

**OPTIMIZATION OF MICROCONTROLLER
BASED AUTOMATIC SOL-GEL METHOD
WITH RESPECT TO OPTICAL PROPERTIES
OF ZnO FILMS**

B.Sc Engineering Thesis

by

Shuva Paul

Roll No: 081026

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
RAJSHAHI UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY

December, 2013

OPTIMIZATION OF MICROCONTROLLER BASED
AUTOMATIC SOL-GEL METHOD WITH RESPECT TO
OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF ZnO FILMS

by

Shuva Paul

Roll No: 081026

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE

in

Electrical and Electronic Engineering

to the

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

RAJSHAHI UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY

December, 2013

DECLARATION

This is to certify that this thesis work “**Optimization of Microcontroller based Automatic Sol-gel Method with respect to Optical Properties of ZnO Films**” by Shuva Paul, bearing Roll no. 081026 has been carried out under my supervision as a requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering.

Thesis Supervisor

.....

Dr. Md. Faruk Hossain

Assistant Professor

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology

Rajshahi-6204, Bangladesh

E-mail: engr.mfhossain@eee.ruet.ac.bd

faruk94_ruet@yahoo.com

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This thesis has been submitted to the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering of Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology (RUET), for the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical & Electronic Engineering. I would like to express my sincere appreciation and great gratitude to all those who gave me the possibility to complete this project and it is my great pleasure to acknowledge the generous contributions of many individuals which have assisted me in writing this paper.

At first, I express my deep sense of gratitude and indebtedness to my thesis supervisor **Dr. Md. Faruk Hossain**, Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical & Electronic Engineering, RUET, for his kind support, encouraging advice and valuable guidance throughout the course of this work. I shall ever remain grateful to him for his amiable demeanor in accomplishing this work; **Dr. Md. Faruk Hossain** has provided me with the design and protocol of the work and has kindly reviewed this manuscript with many helpful suggestions.

Also, I would like to thank the Department of Electrical & Electronic Engineering and its laboratory staff for providing me with the equipment, materials and support during the duration of this project. Moreover, I would like to thank all of my respected teachers and classmates for their kind co-operation.

Finally, I would like to express my gratitude to my family for their never-ending love, encouragement, and patience in every step of my study. I am very thankful to God for having all you great people around me.

ABSTRACT

In conventional sol-gel method having uniform thickness of ZnO thin films is very difficult as constant withdrawing rate cannot be maintained manually. But inclusion of automatic dipping and withdrawing system for sol-gel method has reduced the problem associated with conventional process.

Firstly, the focus of this thesis is on the optimization of previously reported automatic sol-gel system with respect to optical properties of ZnO thin films. With this aim, using zinc acetate, ethanol, diethanolamine and de-ionized water, four sets of ZnO films has been prepared by the automatic sol-gel method. The films have been decomposed at 300⁰C for 30 min and, after giving final coating, have been annealed at 500⁰C for 2 h. Optical transmittance measurements of the deposited films have been carried out with UV/Visible spectrometer at 300-900 wavelengths. Comparison between automatic sol-gel derived and conventional sol-gel derived films have been made. The prepared ZnO films have been found to be highly transparent in the visible range. The average transmittance of ZnO films has been found to above 90% in the visible range with high absorbance in the UV-region and the both direct and indirect band gap have been found to be with acceptable value.

Secondly, for the first time a digital sol-gel system has been introduced in this thesis not only with respect to Bangladesh but globally. There have been some major problems associated with the previously reported automatic sol-gel system and all of them have been overcome in this work. Microcontroller based digital system has been adorned with LCD display, matrix keypad, stepper motor, rack pinion and improved substrate holder and beaker base. Special features of this system are as following: possible to use different lengths of substrate (1-70 mm); variable and separate dipping and withdrawing rate (1-90 mm/min); smooth and vibration free dipping and withdrawing through rack pinion; giving input through matrix keypad; observing whole process through display unit.

CONTENTS

Topic	Page No.
DECLARATION	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	ii
ABSTRACT	iii
CHAPTER-1 :INTRODUCTION	
1.1. Introduction and Motivation	2
1.2. Fundamentals of Sol-gel Method	3
1.3. Literature Review	4
1.4. Main Objectives of the Thesis	5
1.5. Outline of the Thesis	6
CHAPTER-2 :BACKGROUND	
2.1. Nanotechnology	8
2.1.1. Introduction	8
2.1.2. Definition of Nanotechnology	8
2.1.3. Conceptual origins	9
2.1.4. Applications of Nanotechnology	10
2.2. Thin Films Technology	14
2.3. Synthesis of Thin Film and Nanostructures	14
2.3.1. Physical Vapour Deposition (PVD)	14
2.3.1.1 Thermal Evaporation	14
2.3.1.2 <i>Sputtering</i>	16
2.3.1.3 <i>Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD)</i>	17
2.3.2 Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD)	17
2.3.2.1 <i>Thermal CVD & LPCVD</i>	18
2.3.2.2 <i>PECVD & LCVD</i>	18
2.3.2.3 <i>MOCVD</i>	18
2.3.2.4 <i>MBE</i>	19
2.3.3 Solution Based Chemistry (SBC)	20
2.3.3.1 <i>Chemical Bath Deposition (CBD)</i>	20

2.3.3.2 <i>Electrochemical Deposition (ECD)</i>	20
2.3.3.3 <i>Sol-Gel Synthesis</i>	21
2.4. ZnO the Novel Material	22
2.4.1. ZnO Crystal Structures	22
2.4.2. Physical properties of ZnO	23

CHAPTER-3 :METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction	26
3.2 Overview on Sol-Gel Process	26
3.3.Fundamental Stages of Sol Gel Dip Coating Technique	28
3.4.Physics and Chemistry of ZnO Derived from Sol-Gel Thin Film Technology	29
3.4.1 Precursors	29
3.4.2 Solvents	29
3.4.3 Additives	30
3.4.4 Mixing of Solution	31
3.4.5 Growth mechanisms	32
3.4.6 Nucleation and growth	32
3.4.7 Film formation	33
3.4.8 Initial Drying Step	33
3.4.9 Final Annealing Process	34
3.3. Conclusion	35

CHAPTER-4 :EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

4.1. Introduction	37
4.2. Operating principle of automatic sol-gel system	37
4.3. Fabrication of ZnO thin films using so-gel process	39
4.3.1. Parameters variation	39
4.3.2. Steps ZnO thin films fabrication	40
4.3.2.1 <i>Cleaning of Substrate</i>	41
4.3.2.2 <i>Preparation of precursor solution</i>	42
4.3.2.3. <i>Substrate dipping and withdrawing</i>	45
4.3.2.4. <i>Heat treatment</i>	45
4.4. Characterization of prepared ZnO films by UV Visible property	45

CHAPTER-5 :RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	
5.1. Introduction	49
5.2. Deposited ZnO films with length controlled automatic sol-gel process	49
5.3. Comparison between automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films	50
5.3.1. For Zinc acetate concentration of 1.0 mol/L	50
5.3.2. For PEG in 1.0 mol/L Zinc acetate solution	52
5.4. Effect of Zinc acetate concentrations at same films thickness	53
5.5. Effect of various zinc acetate concentrations at same number of coatings	54
5.6. Investigation of the effect of addition of PEG content in zinc acetate precursor solution	56
5.7. Varying thickness of ZnO films on same zinc acetate concentration	57
5.7.1. 1.0 mo/L concentrated Zinc acetate solution	57
5.7.2. 1.2 mo/L concentrated Zinc acetate solution	58
5.8. Optimized parameters for automatic sol-gel method	59
CHAPTER-6 :DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL SOL-GEL SYSTEM	
6.1. Introduction	62
6.2. Problems and proposed improvements of existing automatic sol-gel system.	62
6.3. Block diagram representation of digital sol-gel system	63
6.4. Complete setup of digital sol-gel system	64
6.5. Operating principle of digital sol-gel system	66
6.6. Internal circuitry arrangements of the digital system	68
CHAPTER-7 :CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK	
7.1. Conclusion	74
7.2. Future work	62
REFERENCES	76
APPENDIX	
List of publications	81

List of Figures

Fig. No.	Captions	Page No.
2.1	Human hair fragment and a network of single-walled carbon nanotubes	08
2.2	Commercial scale applications of nanoparticles	10
2.3	Photocatalytic Hydrogen Productions	11
2.4	Filtering process using different structural membranes that filter out specific contaminants	12
2.5	Images of Module of DSSC	13
2.6	Concept drawing of a platform for drug metabolism analysis based on multi-walled carbon nanotubes	13
2.7	Schematic representation of thermal evaporation	15
2.8	Schematic arrangements of dc sputtering method	16
2.9	Schematic arrangements of PLD	17
2.10	Schematic diagram of CVD	18
2.11	Schematic representation of MBE	19
2.12	Zinc Oxide Crystal Structures (a) Wurtzite, (b) zincblende, (c) rock salt	23
3.1	Various steps in the sol-gel process to control the final morphology of the product	27
3.2	Stages of sol-gel dip coating process	28
3.3	Chemical equilibria taking place in the initial solutions followed by Hydrolysis and condensation	31
3.4	Thin Film Formation Steps under heat treatment	34
3.5	TG-DTA curve for ZnO xerogel	35
4.1	Image of complete setup of automatic dipping and withdrawing system	38
4.2	All variations made in this work for preparing ZnO thin films	39
4.3	Sol-gel dip coating processes for ZnO thin films deposition	40
4.4	Glass microslides for thin films deposition	41
4.5	Electronic Ultrasonic cleaner used for cleaning substrate	42
4.6	Magnetic stirrer used for stirring solution	44

4.7	Precursor solution after (a) mixing ZAD and EtOH, (b) after mixing DEA and H ₂ O, and (c) after hydrolyzing.	45
4.8	Characterization of optical properties (a) UV/Visible Spectrometer, and (b) example of Tauc plot for band gap calculation.	47
5.1	Images of ZnO thin films covered with different length of substrate prepared by length controlled automatic sol-gel process	59
5.2	Images of ZnO thin films (a) automatic and (b) conventional sol-gel derived.	50
5.3	Transmittance spectra of automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO thin films	50
5.4	Optical absorbance spectra of automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films	51
5.5	Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ of ZnO thin films for (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition($n=1/2$).	51
5.6	Optical properties with PEG for automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance	52
5.7	Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO thin films with 1.0 g PEG showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition($n=1/2$).	52
5.8	Transmittance spectra for ZnO films of same thickness for various zinc acetate concentrations.	53
5.9	Optical absorbance spectra of ZnO films of same thickness for various zinc acetate concentrations.	54
5.10	Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films of same thickness showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition($n=1/2$).	54
5.11	Optical properties of ZnO films with same number of coatings for various zinc acetate concentrations showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance	55
5.12	Optical properties with various PEG contented ZnO films showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance	56
5.13	Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various PEG content showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect	57

	allowed transition($n=1/2$	
5.14	Optical properties ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance	57
5.15	Plot of $(\alpha hv)^n$ vs. hv for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition($n=1/2$).	58
5.16	Optical properties ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.2 mol/L showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance.	59
5.17	Plot of $(\alpha hv)^n$ vs. hv for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.2 mol/L showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition($n=1/2$).	59
6.1	Limitations and improvements on existing automatic sol-gel system	62
6.2	block diagram representation of digital sol-gel system	63
6.3	Complete setup of digital sol-gel system	64
6.4	Close view of rack and pinion showing in (a) front view and (b) side view	65
6.5	Substrate holder without substrate showing in (a) front view, (b) side view and (c) showing substrate holder with substrate	66
6.6	Operating principle of digital sol-gel system	67
6.7	Complete circuit diagram of digital system showing in (a) dc power supply unit, and (b) interconnection of microcontroller with stepper motor, keypad and LCD display	69
6.8	Architecture of matrix keypad	70
6.9	Pulse sequences of microcontroller to run the stepper motor	71
6.10	Electrical connections of equipments in project board	72
6.11	Electrical connections of equipments in PCB board	72

List of Tables

Fig. No.	Title	Page No.
2.1	Thin films and nanostructures synthesis methods and their advantages and limitations	21
2.2	Basic physical parameters of ZnO at room temperature	24
4.1	No. of layers given to maintain ~500 nm thickness of ZnO films for various concentrations	39
4.2	Amounts of chemical reagents used in this work for different molar concentrations	43
5.1	Optimized parameters for automatic sol-gel method	60

CHAPTER-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction and Motivation

Nanotechnology has developed a bridge among all the fields of science and technology. Materials and structures with low dimensions have excellent properties which enable them to play a crucial role in the rapid progress of the fields of science. With these amazing properties, one dimensional nanostructures have become the back bone of research in all the fields of natural sciences. The emergence of nanotechnology in the 1980s was caused by the convergence of experimental advances such as the invention of the scanning tunneling microscope in 1981 and the discovery of fullerenes in 1985, with the elucidation and popularization of a conceptual framework for the goals of nanotechnology beginning with the 1986 publication of the book “*Engines of Creation*”. The field was subject to growing public awareness and controversy in the early 2000s, with prominent debates about both its potential implications as well as the feasibility of the applications. In the past few years, nanomaterials have attracted tremendous international interest, investment and effort both in scientific research and in industrial development because of their potential applications in various fields [1-4].

Nanoporous materials are one of subset of nanomaterials. With their unique porous structure in nanometer dimensions, they can be used in various applications such as ion exchange, separation, catalysis, sensor, biological molecular recognition and purification [5]. According to the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) [6] porous materials can be classified into three categories: 1) micropores are smaller than 2 nm in diameter; 2) mesopores are between 2 to 50 nm; 3) macropores are larger than 50 nm. But this definition is somewhat conflict with the more broadened definition of nanoporous materials. The term of “nanoporous” currently refers to the class of porous materials having pore diameters between 1 and 100 nm. It is noted that nanoporous materials actually encompass some micro and macro porous materials and all mesoporous materials [1]. Sol-gel technology has been used extensively in the synthesis of nanoporous materials [7-8]. The overall sol-gel process, as the name implies, usually involves two stages: precursors initially form high molecular weight but still soluble oligomeric intermediates, a sol, and the intermediates further link together to form a three-dimensional crosslinked network, a gel. The precursors for a sol-gel reaction could be either inorganic salts or organic compounds, such as metal alkoxides.

Thin films coating technologies have drawn a considerable attention from the last several decades due to its functional advantages over bulk materials. Thin-film technology

is simultaneously one of the oldest arts and one of the newest sciences. Involvement with thin films dates to the metal ages of antiquity. Consider the ancient craft of gold beating, which has been practiced continuously for at least four millenia. Gold's great malleability enables it to be hammered into leaf of extraordinary thinness while its beauty and resistance to chemical degradation have earmarked its use for durable ornamentation and protection purposes. Today, gold leaf can be machine-beaten to 0.1 micron and to 0.05 micron when beaten by a skilled craftsman. In this form it is invisible sideways and quite readily absorbed by the skin. Now-a-days thin films are being realized using many processes which can be broadly categorized as physical deposition and chemical deposition. Chemical deposition is also categorized into wet solution based and gas phase based. Among wet solution processes Sol-gel process is the most popular method for thin films deposition.

1.2. Fundamentals of Sol-gel Method

The process of thin films formation by sol-gel process is quite simple. A solution containing the desired oxide or non-oxide precursor is prepared. It is applied to a substrate by spinning, dipping, or draining, or spraying. The process is able to apply a coating to the inside and the outside of complex shapes simultaneously. The films are typically 200 nm - 10 μm thick, uniform over large areas, and adherent. The sol-gel coating process is inexpensive, especially in comparison to any deposition techniques that involve vacuum. Coatings can be applied to metals, plastics, woods, papers and ceramics. Typically, the coatings are applied at room temperature, though most need to be calcined and densified by heating. Both amorphous and crystalline coatings can be obtained. [9]

The basis for the sol-gel coating process is the hydrolysis of metal alkoxide compounds in alcoholic solutions. Alkoxide molecules exist as low molecular weight species, usually monomers or small oligomers, depending on the particular alkoxides used, the solvent and other factors. In principle, any precursors of a suitable compound which can be hydrolyzed could be used. The sol-gel reaction of these species occurs via hydrolysis of the M-OR moiety and polycondensation reactions involving the resulting M-OH group. Water acts as the "initiator" and is usually externally added. Water can also be generated in situ by condensation reactions such as the formation of esters by the condensation of carboxylic acids and alcohols. Acids or bases are used as catalysts for these reactions. The initial viscosity of the sol derived from polymeric precursors is rather

low and in many cases is similar to that of water (-1mPas). If the polycondensation reactions are allowed to occur to a significant extent, the original sol can transform into a gel. The reaction of metal alkoxides with water is known as the hydrolysis reaction [10]. After the conversion into depositable colloidal sol by hydrolysis and polycondensation reaction, the sol can be applied on the substrates and cured during and after contact of the substrate with the coating solution. From a practical view, the reaction rate for the hydrolysis and condensation for the gel formation should be higher than the crystallization rate from the solution, in order to obtain uniform, transparent coatings. For this reason alkoxides are preferred [11].

1.3. Literature Review

Among various functional materials, metal oxide films are very attractive for many applications due to their good electrical and optical properties. Recently, ZnO thin films of microstructures and nanostructures have been widely studied due to its novel non-linear optical properties and as well as for its multifunctionalities [12-13]. ZnO crystallizes in the wurtzite hexagonal structure with c-axis orientation and it is naturally n-type semiconductor due to defects such as oxygen deficiency and zinc excess [14]. It can be a cheaper substitute to wurtzite GaN for optoelectronic applications in the blue and UV regions due to larger free exciton binding energy of 60 meV, compared to GaN of 26 meV, which ensures an efficient excitonic emission even at room temperature [14-15]. In addition, the electron mobility of ZnO ($115\text{-}155\text{ cm}^2\text{ V}^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1}$) at room temperature is higher than that of TiO_2 ($<10^5\text{ cm}^2\text{ V}^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1}$) [16]. As a result, with similar band gap of TiO_2 , ZnO nanoparticles are being widely used in the Grätzel-type solar cells [17]. Now-a-days, doped and/or un-doped ZnO are being widely used as transparent conductive oxide (TCO) due to high transparency in visible range. Moreover, ZnO is chemically and mechanically stable, non-toxic and high abundant [12]. As a result, it is being widely used in gas sensors, varistors, UV detectors, thin film transistor, spintronic devices, especially due to its wide band gap energy of 3.37 eV at room temperature [14].

ZnO thin films can be realized using vapor phase processing and wet solution processing. Vapor phase growth techniques, such as molecular beam epitaxy [18], metal-organic chemical vapor deposition [19] and sputtering deposition [20] require sophisticated equipment set-up and they are not economical as far as the manufacturing cost is concerned. On the other hand, wet solution processing that include spray pyrolysis

[20], spin coating [77], sol-gel process [21-23] offer advantages in terms of the manufacturing cost, are being explored recently. Among the methods, sol-gel process is most effective to deposit thin films for some reasons: simplicity, inexpensive preparation of homogeneous thin film, excellent compositional control, lower crystallization temperature, large area coatings and good optical coatings [13]. In order to produce thin, transparent, multi-component oxide layers of many compositions on various substrates no other deposition technique is efficient rather than sol-gel process [24].

The optical and structural properties of sol-gel derived ZnO thin films depend critically on several parameters such as pre heating and annealing temperature, concentration of solution and film thickness [15]. Among these factors film thickness is directly related to the resistivity, crystallites size and orientation of ZnO films [25]. It has been reported that film thickness of sol-gel derived ZnO film is greatly dependent on the withdrawing rate and for uniform thickness of the films withdrawing rate must be constant [26]. But in conventional sol-gel process [21-23] dipping and withdrawing process is done manually, hence maintaining constant and smooth dipping or withdrawing rate is quite difficult. The remedy of this problem is to implement automatic dipping and withdrawing system [27].

1.4. Main Objectives of the Thesis

Previously reported automatic sol-gel system [27] was not optimized with any properties of thin films. First aim of this thesis work is to optimize the automatic sol-gel system and secondly, to develop a digital sol-gel system. The main objectives of this thesis work are given below:

- Study of different thin films deposition techniques.
- Preparation of ZnO thin films using automatic sol-gel dip coating technique
- Observation of the resultant effect for parameters variation on fabricating process.
- Characterization of prepared ZnO thin films with optical properties
- Optimization of the automatic sol-gel system with respect to optical properties of ZnO films.
- To develop a digital sol-gel system overcoming the problems of previously reported automatic sol-gel system.

1.5. Outline of the Thesis

The whole thesis paper is arranged with seven chapters. Overview of these chapters is given below.

Chapter 1:

This chapter deals with the introduction and motivation to this work. After describing literature survey objectives of this thesis work has been clarified.

Chapter 2:

In this chapter as a background of this work a brief discussion about nanotechnology and its applications, about thin film technology, about ZnO as a promising material oxide have been given.

Chapter 3:

In this chapter methodology of this work has been described. In order to deposit ZnO thin films sol-gel process have been used in this work.

Chapter 4:

Experimental procedures for depositing ZnO thin films using automatic sol-gel method have been fully described in this chapter.

Chapter 5:

This chapter is about the experimental results and discussions that includes optical properties of prepared ZnO thin films, comparison between automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO thin films and optimization of automatic sol-gel system.

Chapter 6:

In order to overcome the limitations of automatic sol-gel system a digital sol-gel system has been. This chapter deals with the modeling and fabrication of digital sol-gel system with necessary figures and circuit diagrams.

Chapter 7:

Finally a conclusion of this work has been given in this chapter and future directions related to the work in this thesis has been also given.

CHAPTER- 2

BACKGROUND

2.1. Nanotechnology

2.1.1. Introduction

Truly *revolutionary* nanotechnology products, materials and applications, such as nanorobotics, are years in the future (some say only a few years; some say many years). What qualifies as "nanotechnology" today is basic research and development that is happening in laboratories all over the world. "Nanotechnology" products that are on the market today are mostly gradually improved products (using *evolutionary* nanotechnology) where some form of nanotechnology enabled material (such as carbon nanotubes, nanocomposite structures or nanoparticles of a particular substance) or nanotechnology process (e.g. nanopatterning or quantum dots for medical imaging) is used in the manufacturing process. In their ongoing quest to improve existing products by creating smaller components and better performance materials, all at a lower cost, the number of companies that will manufacture "nanoproducts" (by this definition) will grow very fast and soon make up the majority of all companies across many industries. Evolutionary nanotechnology should therefore be viewed as a process that gradually will affect most companies and industries.

2.1.2. Definition of Nanotechnology

So what exactly is *nanotechnology*? One of the problems facing nanotechnology is the confusion about its definition. Most definitions revolve around the study and control of phenomena and materials at length scales below 100 nm and quite often they make a comparison with a human hair, which is about 80,000 nm wide. Some definitions include a reference to molecular systems and devices and nanotechnology 'purists' argue that any definition of nanotechnology needs to include a reference to "functional systems".

Figure 2.1. Human hair fragment and a network of single-walled carbon nanotubes [28]

It seems that a size limitation of nanotechnology to the 1-100 nm range, the area where size-dependant quantum effects come to bear, would exclude numerous materials and devices, especially in the pharmaceutical area, and some experts caution against a rigid definition based on a sub-100 nm size. Another important criteria for the definition is the requirement that the nano-structure is man-made. Otherwise you would have to include every naturally formed biomolecule and material particle, in effect redefining much of chemistry and molecular biology as 'nanotechnology.' The most important requirement for the nanotechnology definition is that the nano-structure has special properties that are exclusively due to its nanoscale proportions.

A good definition that is practical and unconstrained by any arbitrary size limitations is here:

The design, characterization, production, and application of structures, devices, and systems by controlled manipulation of size and shape at the nanometer scale (atomic, molecular, and macromolecular scale) that produces structures, devices, and systems with at least one novel/superior characteristic or property.

2.1.3. Conceptual origins

The American physicist Richard Feynman lectured, "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom," at an American Physical Society meeting at Caltech on December 29, 1959. Feynman had described a process by which the ability to manipulate individual atoms and molecules might be developed [29].

Chris Toumey, a cultural anthropologist at the University of South Carolina, found that the published versions of Feynman's talk had a negligible influence, as measured by citations in the scientific literature, and not much more influence in the decade after the Scanning Tunneling Microscope was invented in 1981. K. Eric Drexler in his 1986 book, *Engines of Creation: The Coming Era of Nanotechnology*, which took the Feynman concept of a billion tiny factories and added the idea that they could make more copies of themselves via computer control instead of control by a human operator; and in a cover article headlined "Nanotechnology" [30] published later that year in a mass-circulation science-oriented magazine, *OMNI*. Toumey's analysis also includes comments from distinguished scientists in nanotechnology who say that "Plenty of Room" did not influence their early work, and in fact most of them had not read it until a later date [31].

2.1.4. Applications of Nanotechnology

Nanoparticles are at the forefront of the nanotechnology wave. They are less than about 100 nm in diameter that exhibit new or enhanced size-dependent properties compared with larger particles of the same material. The ability to fabricate and control the structure of nanoparticles allows the scientist and engineer to influence the resulting properties and, ultimately, design materials to give the desired properties. The current and potential applications for nanoparticles are growing and cover an extremely broad range of markets industries including biomedical & cancer treatment, renewable energy, environmental protection, pharmaceuticals, personal care, surface coatings, plastics, textiles, food, building materials, electronics, automotives, etc. The following Fig 2.2 shows the areas where nanoparticles can be applied.

Figure 2.2. Commercial scale applications of nanoparticles [32]

Some recent applications of nanotechnology are briefly discussed below:

Hydrogen generation:- Photoelectrocatalytic water splitting is widely recognized as one of the most promising routes to large-scale production of hydrogen as a potential fuel for renewable energy. Among the various catalysts, the noble metal palladium has attracted attention as one of the most versatile candidates utilized in hydrogen-relevant reactions [33]. In particular, Pd immobilized on diverse supports, including carbon, silicates, amorphous or mesoporous silica, and porous biomaterials or polymers, exhibits remarkable performance in organic transformations and especially coupling and hydrogenation reactions [34]. Fig. 2.3 shows a schematic arrangement of water splitting for hydrogen generation. When attached to a p-type semiconductor, the photocatalyst will form half of a photo-electrochemical cell for splitting water. The water-splitting photocell will be completed by connecting the hydrogen-generating photo-electrode to another electrode, which is capable of generating oxygen.

Figure 2.3. Photocatalytic Hydrogen Productions [35]

Filtration:- A strong influence of photochemistry on waste-water treatment, air purification and energy storage devices is to be expected. Mechanical or chemical methods can be used for effective filtration techniques. One class of filtration techniques is based on the use of membranes with suitable hole sizes, whereby the liquid is pressed through the membrane. Nanoporous membranes are suitable for a mechanical filtration with extremely small pores smaller than 10 nm (“nanofiltration”) and may be composed of nanotubes. Nanofiltration is mainly used for the removal of ions or the separation of

Figure 2.4. Filtering process using different structural membranes that filter out specific contaminants

different fluids. On a larger scale, the membrane filtration technique is named ultrafiltration, which works down to between 10 and 100 nm. One important field of application for ultrafiltration is medical purposes as can be found in renal dialysis. Magnetic nanoparticles offer an effective and reliable method to remove heavy metal contaminants from waste water by making use of magnetic separation techniques. Using nanoscale particles increases the efficiency to absorb the contaminants and is comparatively inexpensive compared to traditional precipitation and filtration methods. Some water-treatment devices incorporating nanotechnology are already on the market, with more in development. Low-cost nanostructured separation membranes methods have been shown to be effective in producing potable water in a recent study [36].

Dye-sensitized solar cell:-A new type of solar cell based on dye-sensitized nanocrystalline titanium dioxide has been developed by M. Grätzel and coworkers [37]. Remarkably high quantum efficiencies have been reported for this type of solar cell (also called nc-DSC), with overall conversion efficiencies up to 11 % [38]. This fact, in combination with the expected relatively easy and low cost manufacturing makes this new technology an interesting alternative for existing solar cell technologies. First application of this type of solar cell will probably be one in which only a low power output is required, since this is easier to achieve. Less stringent efficiency requirements leave room for increased flexibility in the manufacturing process of these cells. This result in lower manufacturing costs and more flexibility in materials choice, opening the way for alternative production processes.

Figure 2.5. Images of Module of DSSC

Nanochip Arrays for Personalized Therapy:-The development of new technologies in personalized therapy is required to increase the fraction of patients that can benefit at best from pharmacological treatments. Average rate of efficacy of drug therapies ranges, for many of the major pathologies, from 20 to 60%; moreover, approximately 7% of hospitalized patients experience serious adverse drug reactions. For this reason, drug therapy needs personalization to the individual patient.

Figure 2.6. Concept drawing of a platform for drug metabolism analysis based on multi-walled carbon nanotubes [39]

At present, the only strategy for personalization of drug therapies is to check the genetic predisposition of patients. Even if this technology represents a great improvement with respect to the traditional approach, the sole knowledge of genotype is not sufficient to achieve the maximum accuracy in drug administration. Recently an implantable,

nanotechnology based, biosensor for drug metabolism analysis has been developed which significantly improves the quality and reliability of drug concentration measurements, providing at the same time a reduction in the cost and time of analysis [39].

2.2. Thin Films Technology

Thin film is the general term used for coatings that are used to modify and increase the functionality of a bulk surface or substrate. They are used to protect surfaces from wear, improve lubricity, improve corrosion and chemical resistance, and provide a barrier to gas penetration. In many cases thin films do not affect the bulk properties of the material. They can, however, totally change the optical, electrical transport, and thermal properties of a surface or substrate, in addition to providing an enhanced degree of surface protection. Thin films have distinct advantages over bulk materials. Because most processes used to deposit thin films are non-equilibrium in nature, the composition of thin films is not constrained by metallurgical phase diagrams. Crystalline phase composition can also be varied to a certain extent by deposition conditions and plasma enhancement. Virtually every property of the thin film depends on and can be modified by the deposition process and not all processes produce materials with the same properties. Microstructure, surface morphology, tribological, electrical, and optical properties of the thin film are all controlled by the deposition process. A single material can be used in several different applications and technologies, and the optimum properties for each application may depend on the deposition process used. Since not all deposit technologies yield the same properties or microstructures, the deposition process must be chosen to fit the required properties and application. [40]

Recently, thin film deposition technology and the science have progressed rapidly in the direction of engineered thin film coatings and surface engineering. Plasmas are used more extensively. Accordingly, advanced thin film deposition processes have been developed and new technologies have been adapted to conventional deposition processes. The market and applications for thin film coatings have also increased astronomically, particularly in the biomedical, display, and energy fields. Engineered materials are the future of thin film technology. Engineered structures such as superlattices, nanolaminates, nanotubes, nanocomposites, smart materials, photonic bandgap materials, molecularly doped polymers, and structured materials all have the capacity to expand and increase the functionality of thin films and coatings used in a variety of applications and provide new

applications. New advanced deposition processes and hybrid processes are being used and developed to deposit advanced thin film materials and structures not possible with conventional techniques a decade ago.

2.3. Synthesis of Thin Film and Nanostructures

A variety of methods has been used for synthesis thin film and nanostructures. For consolidation, methods have been categorized as either physical vapour deposition (PVD), CVD, or solution based chemistry (SBC), PVD and CVD fall into the category of gas-phase approach where high vacuum and/or elevated temperature are normally required. Each respective method can be sub-divided into the individual technique that will be introduced in the following sections.

2.3.1. Physical Vapour Deposition (PVD)

PVD operates when a material is physically released from a source and transferred to a substrate. It describes the solidification of a vapour directly onto a surface such that no chemical reaction takes place. If a chemical reaction does occur with the vapour, and /or with the deposition surface, then the process is not PVD but rather CVD. The three most common and important PVD technologies for thin films deposition are thermal evaporation, pulsed laser deposition (PLD), and sputtering, each of which will be introduced below:

2.3.1.1 Thermal Evaporation

The thermal evaporation basically follows the vapour-solid (V-S) mechanism. Usually material powders are placed inside a vacuum chamber, where the vacuum condition is kept in the range of 10^{-2} to 10^{-9} Torr. The powder will be heated up by a heating source to its vapour point once the appropriate pressure within the vacuum chamber is reached. The vaporized materials will condense along the cooler surfaces in the vacuum chambers,

Figure 2.7. Schematic representation of thermal evaporation

as well as on the collection substrate. By varying the experimental temperature, pressure in the chamber, atmosphere and facility configuration thin films and various nanostructures can be produced by this method.

Electron beam, radio frequency (RF) inductive, and resistive heating are the heating sources typically used in thermal evaporation. Electron beam and RF inductive heating are used to create localized heating of the source material, which have been limited to produce highly oriented thin films. Resistive heating is a non-localized heating source and commonly used for furnace applications. For example, a tube furnace with appropriate design and control can create a specific temperature gradient along the tube, which is useful for nanostructure production.

2.3.1.2 Sputtering

Sputtering is the removal of surface atoms via high energy ions. The modern sputtering system uses a magnetron sputtering configuration, where a strong magnetic field is applied to concentrate the plasma near the target to increase the deposition rate. Certain level of vacuum is required for the sputtering system. During the experiment, after evacuation of foreign gas, an inert gas normally Ar as the working gas, is introduced into the vacuum chamber where the source material target and substrates have been placed in. Then a direct current (DC) or RF power supply is used to ionize the inert gas so as to produce charged plasma. The ions are accelerated to the surface of the target, and bombarding the atoms of the source material out of the target. Resultantly, some of those atoms condense on the substrate to form films.

Figure 2.8. Schematic arrangements of dc sputtering method

A bias voltage sometimes is applied to the substrate to assist the deposition, and enhance the adhesion properties of the film to the substrate. The substrate can be heated to improve the crystal quality of the growing film. Normally DC sputtering is used for conductive target, but not suitable to insulating materials due the build-up of positive charge on the

target materials, while an RF power can be used to solve this problem. Doping is possible to achieve with sputtering system by the means of introducing gases containing dopant elements or mixing dopant materials into the target.

2.3.1.3 Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD)

PLD is another popular technique for the synthesis of thin films and nanostructure materials. High vacuum condition is also required for this process. A laser beam is focused through vacuum onto the surface of a target material during the deposition. Sufficient high flux density and short pulse duration is requested to heat up the target rapidly to its evaporation temperature so as to form a vapour plume. The laser ablation produced vapour plume that has the similar stoichiometry of the target material, which is one of the major advantage of PLD. Once the vapour plume has been formed, it is collected onto a cooler substrate that promotes nucleation and growth of crystalline films. Doping can be conducted relatively easily through PLD by using targets with designed composition or a multi target system, and the doping level can be precisely controlled and monitored during the deposition. The main practical limitation of PLD is its relatively low duty cycle and incorporation of particulates in the deposited films. Up scaling for industrial production and deposition of zinc oxide on large area substrates is still a major concern.

Figure 2.9. Schematic arrangements of PLD

2.3.2 Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD)

CVD involves the chemical reaction between the vaporized source material and source gases, and/or with the deposition surface. The product of the reaction condenses during the formation of a solid material within the reaction vessel where the pressure and gas flow are controlled.

Figure 2.10. Schematic diagram of CVD

The most common CVD techniques used to deposit ZnO are thermal CVD, low pressure CVD (LPCVD), plasma-enhanced CVD (PECVD), laser CVD (LCVD) metal-organic CVD (MOCVD), MBE, and atomic layer deposition (ALD), classified by the differences of the vacuum control level, heating source and reactants gas types etc. For each of these methods, a vacuum chamber with gas flow control is required. Some of the specific CVD techniques are introduced below.

2.3.2.1 Thermal CVD & LPCVD

The experimental setup for thermal CVD is similar to the thermal evaporation. The required pressure level is 10^{-3} Torr for the process. A solid source could be placed upstream. The solid is vaporized through heating, which is transported by a carrier gas that feeds the catalyst and source material for nanowire growth. LPCVD deposition is an old technique in industry for oxide film growth. In some research, it is the interchangeable term with the thermal CVD, but its working pressure range is slightly different. In LPCVD deposition process, the pressure is controlled to under 0.1 Torr.

2.3.2.2 PECVD & LCVD

In Comparison with thermal CVD and LPCVD, PECVD are performed at much lower temperature, down to 300°C . The plasma is generated to compensate the low temperature, and increase the energy available to the chemical reaction. This technique is usually used for ZnO film preparation. In LCVD, laser ablation with controlled doses is used as the heating source, which leads to precise dimension and doping controls for nanostructure. Super-lattices and core shell structures can be produced by this method.

2.3.2.3 MOCVD

MOCVD is almost identical to the other types of CVD, only that metal-organic precursors are use to catalyze the chemical reaction. MOCVD needs to be carried out at a very high

level of vacuum and elevated temperature, and has been extensively used for synthesis of ZnO thin films and nanostructures. Doping is relatively easy to be conducted. However, metal-organic compounds are usually more expensive than inorganic compounds.

2.3.2.4 MBE

MBE is recognized as a technique for preparing high-quality layers, superlattices and hetero-structures with excellent thickness control, composition uniformity, and sharp dopant profiles. The term “beam” is used because the process takes place at ultra high vacuum chamber, and thus the mean-free-paths of the source materials vapours are sufficiently large to prevent all atomic interaction before arrive at the substrate. The vapours are from element sources with high purity which are slowly heated in individual quasi-knudsen cells, and released into the vacuum chamber by computer-controlled shutters. Upon condensation onto the single-crystal substrate, the elements from the vapours will start to interact with each other as well as with the substrates, and then atomic layers are epitaxially grown one layer at a time. The crystal quality and layer thickness can be monitored by reflective high energy electron diffraction (RHEED) during the crystal growth. MBE method can produce very high quality single crystal ZnO film and nanostructures. However, the MBE system is very expensive and the operation conditions must be accurately monitored and controlled. It is therefore more suitable for scientific research in the laboratory scale.

Figure 2.11. Schematic representation of MBE

2.3.3 Solution Based Chemistry (SBC)

Compared to vapour phase approaches, solution growth methods have the advantages of low growth temperature, potential for easy scaling up, and simplicity for fabrication of some nanostructures. Methods for the synthesis of ZnO nanostructures in chemical solutions are commonly conducted at relative low temperatures (60-300°C). Solution processes are thermodynamically equilibrium processes, and thus the precise control of growth process, impurity, doping and product uniformity are the major problems. In addition, chemical waste treatment also needs to be addressed to deal with the environment issues in the future for commercialization. However, from cost efficiency point of view, a low-cost chemical synthesis with high yield undoubtedly is suitable for commercialization of nanostructure materials. Several solutions based chemical synthesis methods are introduced below.

2.3.3.1 Chemical Bath Deposition (CBD)

The term of CBD is referred to the techniques that produce a solid structure in a single immersion through a control of the formation kinetics of the solid, normally without changing the metals' oxidation states. ZnO nanorods can be produce by CBD at a temperature as low as 60°C. ZnO seeds are required to initialize the oriented nanowires growth. The solution containing ZnO(NO₃)₂ and hexamethyltetramine (HMTA) is used, the PH value can vary from 5 to 12. The main reactions involved in this process are:

The deposition rate is mainly dominated by HMTA decomposition rate (reaction 1), which is strongly temperature dependent. Therefore, by adjusting reaction temperature, ZnO nanostructures with different feature can be obtained. The normal reaction temperature range is ranging from 60°C to 200°C. ZnO nanostructures such as nanorods, nanowires, nanoplate, and nanospheres can be produce by varying the reaction temperature, solution pH value, Zn salt type, basic reagents, and additives. However, the ZnO nanostructures produced by this method normally do not have good adhesion to the substrate.

2.3.3.2 Electrochemical Deposition (ECD)

ZnO can be deposited cathodically from an aqueous solution of Zn salt in the presence of dissolved oxygen. Nano-rods, nano-tubes and nano-porous film have been successfully synthesized by ECD [76]. The porous ZnO film is studied intensively for the DSSC

applications. To produce porous ZnO films by ECD, shape-control reagents are commonly added to create desired porosity.

2.3.3.3 Sol-Gel Synthesis

ZnO thin films, nanocrystals, nanorods with preferred crystallographic orientation have been synthesized using the sol-gel method. “Sol” is referred to a colloidal suspension. The formation of Sol will develop inorganic networks, and as the networks form in a continuous liquid phase, it becomes “gel”. The precursors for synthesizing these colloids consist of a metal/metalloid surrounded by various reactive ligands. Metal alkoxides are most popular because they react readily with water. At the functional group level, three reactions are involved in the sol-gel process: hydrolysis, alcohol condensation, and water condensation. However, a number of factors such as PH, temperature and time of reaction, reagent concentrations, catalyst nature and concentration, aging temperature and time, and drying have impacts on the characteristics and properties of a particular sol-gel inorganic network by affecting the rate of hydrolysis and condensation reactions.

Table 2.1. Thin films and nanostructures synthesis methods and their advantages and limitations

Category	Techniques	Advantages	Limitations
PVD (gas phase)	Thermal evaporation	High quality Nanostructures variety No chemical waste	High temperature Vacuum Small scale Bad adhesion to substrate
	Sputtering	Doping Good adhesion to substrate Low temperature capability	High vacuum Nanostructures difficulty
	PLD	High quality Variety of products Precise control of composition Doping profile	High vacuum Expensive equipment Small scale up
CVD (gas phase)	Thermal CVD & LPCVD	Industrial used technique Nanostructures capable	High temperature Vacuum
	PECVD	Lower operation temperature Film deposition	Nanostructure difficulty Vacuum condition
	LCVD	Precise control of nanostructure Dimension and doping	Vacuum Facility requirement
	MOCVD	High quality Products variety Nanostructures capable	Toxic chemical High vacuum High temperature Expensive facility

	MBE	Ultra high crystal quality Nanostructure capable Precise control of doping profile	Ultra high vacuum Expensive equipment Critical operation requirement Small scale
SBC	CBD	Low temperature Easy operation Large variety of nanostructures High yield, low cost Scale up capable	Product quality Uniformity Precise control Environment issues Doping problem Bad adhesion to substrate
	ECD	Low temperature Traditional method Nanostructures capable Porous film Low cost Scale up capable	Product quality Uniformity Precise control Environment issues
	Sol-gel	Low temperature Easy operation Large variety of nanostructures High yield Low cost Scale up capable	Product quality Uniformity Precise control Environment issues

2.4. ZnO the Novel Material

During the last decade, new nanomaterials/nanostructures based device structures have attracted a great attention because of their fascinating properties and potential as building blocks for electronics, optoelectronics, and sensor applications. These properties make the ZnO a promising material for the fabrication of the nanodevices such as light emitting diodes, electrochemical sensors, ultra-violet (UV) detectors, nanogenerators and etc. Currently, zinc oxide is the most studied material among metal oxides due to its broad application list related to its semiconducting, optical and piezoelectric properties and etc., respectively. For instance, ZnO-based devices can be used in optoelectronics, sensors/transducers and lasers etc.

2.4.1. ZnO Crystal Structures

ZnO crystallizes in three forms – hexagonal Wurtzite, zincblende and cubic rock salt. The predominant form is hexagonal Wurtzite since this structure is the most stable at ambient temperature and pressure. This hexagonal form has two interpenetrating sub lattices of Zn^{2+} and O^{2-} which make up the alternating basal planes. The zinc to oxygen coordination number is four with the cations surrounded by four anions in the corners of a tetrahedron and vice versa. The tetrahedral arrangement of atoms in the Wurtzite structure results is a non-centrosymmetric structure which gives rise to a dipole moment. This characteristic of

zinc oxide Wurtzite is believed to be what gives rise to some of its unique properties such as piezoelectricity.

The hexagonal lattice constants are $a = 3.25 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.2 \text{ \AA}$. The ratio c/a is about 1.60 which is close to the ideal value for a hexagonal cell i.e., $c/a = 1.633$. Zinc oxide crystals exhibit several typical surface orientations. The most important surfaces are the basal plane, the prism plane, and the pyramidal plane crystal faces. Zinc ions are located on alternate basal planes to the oxygen ions. To achieve transparency and good conductivity the preferred crystal growth is in the (002) plane where atomic density is highest.

Zinc oxide may form the rock salt structure at relatively high pressures. The rock salt structure is common for materials where the coordination number for the cations and the anions is six. A unit cell for the zinc oxide rock salt structure can be modeled with anions arranged on the face centered and corner sites of the cubic unit with one cation at the center of the cube and one centered on each of the 12 cube edges. The zincblende structure can be formed when the crystal is grown on a cubic substrate. Like the rock salt structure, zincblende is a cubic crystal structure but the coordination number is four. This structure is characterized by two interpenetrating face centered cubic structures formed by the alternating anions and cations. A unit cell for this structure can be modeled with the anions occupying the face centered and corner sites of the cube and the cations occupying half of the tetrahedral positions.

Figure 2.12. Zinc Oxide Crystal Structures (a) Wurtzite, (b) zincblende, (c) rock salt

2.4.2. Physical properties of ZnO

Zinc Oxide is an inorganic compound which usually appears as a white powder. There are few basic physical parameters for the ZnO at the room temperature which is listed in table

2.2. The chemical bonds that form Zinc Oxide are borderline between ionic and covalent bonds though they lean towards being ionic. ZnO has relatively low solubility in water (1.6×10^{-6} g/cm³ or 2×10^{-6} moles/liter) and even less solubility in Ethanol. There is still some uncertainty in the values of the thermal conductivity due to the presence of some crystal defects in the material. In addition, a stable and reproducible p-type doping in ZnO is still a challenge and cannot be achieved. The findings regarding the values related to the mobility of hole and its effective mass are still arguable. The values of the carrier mobility can surely be enhanced after achieving good control on the defects in the material.

Table 2.2: Basic physical parameters of ZnO at room temperature

Parameters	Values
Lattice constants at 300 K	a = 0.32495 nm, c = 0.52069 nm
Density	5.67526 g/cm ³
Molecular mass	81.389 g/mol
Melting point	2250 K
Electron effective mass	0.28 m ₀
Hole effective mass	0.59 m ₀
Static dielectric constant	8.656
Refractive index	2.008, 2.029
Bandgap energy at 300 K	3.37 eV
Exciton binding energy	60 meV
Thermal conductivity	0.6 - 1.16 W/Km
Specific heat	0.125 cal/g°C
Thermal constant at 573	1200 mV/K
Electron mobility	~210 cm ² /Vs

CHAPTER- 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

ZnO thin films are being widely researched as a result of their usefulness in emerging renewable energy and sensor applications. In the renewable energy area, ZnO thin films are showing promise as window layers, antireflective layers, and electrode materials. If there is a fabrication method for thin films, it has likely been studied for fabricating Zinc Oxide thin films. For example, recent reports have been published of studies where Zinc Oxide thin films were made via molecular beam epitaxy [41], dc and rf sputtering [42-43], chemical vapor deposition [44], metal-organic chemical vapor deposition [45], pulsed laser deposition [46], spray pyrolysis [47] and of course sol-gel [48-50]. Vapor phase growth techniques, such as molecular beam epitaxy, metal-organic chemical vapor deposition and sputtering deposition require sophisticated equipment set-up and they are not economical as far as the manufacturing cost is concerned. On the other hand, wet solution processing that include spray pyrolysis, spin coating [77], sol-gel process offer advantages in terms of the manufacturing cost, are being explored recently. Among the methods, sol-gel process is most effective to deposit thin films for some reasons: simplicity, inexpensive preparation of homogeneous thin film, excellent compositional control, lower crystallization temperature, large area coatings and good optical coatings.

In this work, as a wet solution processing technique sol-gel route was used to prepare ZnO thin films. A detail review on sol-gel processes of ZnO film preparation has been reported by Lamia Znaidi [51]. Depending on the nature of the molecular precursors, two sol-gel routes are currently used: metal alkoxides in organic solvents or metal salts in aqueous solutions [52]. The main methods of ZnO preparation are intermediate between the two sol-gel methods since they use metal salts in alcoholic solutions. ZnO films are obtained starting from inorganic salts such as nitrates, chlorides, perchlorates or organic salts like acetates and acetylacetonates, dissolved in alcoholic media. In such media the process involves two steps. The first one consists of in situ formation of alkoxide or alkoxy-complexes. In the second step, these complexes undergo transformation through hydrolysis and polymerization to lead to the oxide.

3.2. Overview on Sol-Gel Process

In general, the sol-gel process consists of the following steps (Figure 2.1) [53]: i) Preparation of a homogeneous solution either by dissolution of metal organic precursors in an organic solvent that is miscible with water, or by dissolution of inorganic salts in water;

ii) conversion of the homogeneous solution into a sol by treatment with a suitable reagent (generally water with or without any acid/base); iii) aging; iv) shaping; and v) thermal treatment/ sintering. The first step in a sol-gel reaction is the formation of an inorganic polymer by hydrolysis and condensation reactions, i.e., the transformation of the molecular precursor into a highly crosslinked solid. Hydrolysis leads to a sol, a dispersion of colloidal particles in a liquid, and further condensation results in a gel, an interconnected, rigid and porous inorganic network enclosing a continuous liquid phase. This transformation is called the sol-gel transition. There are two possibilities to dry the gels. Upon removal of the pore liquid under supercritical conditions, the network does not collapse and aerogels are produced. When the gel is dried under ambient conditions, shrinkage of the pores occurs, yielding a xerogel. One of the highly attractive features of the sol-gel process is the possibility to shape the material into any desired form such as monoliths, films, fibers, and monosized powders, and subsequently to convert it into a ceramic material by heat treatment.

Figure 3.1 Various steps in the sol-gel process to control the final morphology of the product.

The sol-gel conversion of metal alkoxides involves two main reaction types: hydrolysis and condensation. During hydrolysis, the alkoxide groups (-OR) are replaced via the

nucleophilic attack of the oxygen atom of a water molecule under release of alcohol and the formation of a meta hydroxide (Equation 3.1). Condensation reactions between two hydroxylated metal species leads to M-O-M bonds under release of water (oxolation) (Equation 3.2), whereas the reaction between a hydroxide and an alkoxide leads to M-O-M bonds under release of an alcohol (alkoxolation) (Equation 3.3).

3.3. Fundamental Stages of Sol Gel Dip Coating Technique

Simply to say sol-gel dip coating consists of dipping a substrate and withdrawal of the substrate from a fluid sol: gravitational draining and solvent evaporation, accompanied by further condensation reactions, result in the deposition of a solid film [54].

Figure 3.2 Stages of sol-gel dip coating process.

Fig. 1 shows the various stage of sol gel dip coating process where at the first stage a precursor solution is made and then hydrolyzed to have clear solution. After that a substrate is immersed into and withdrawn from the solution with a well-defined speed under controlled temperature and atmospheric conditions. Withdrawing the substrate causes to form wet layer on the substrate and gelation of the layer by solvent evaporation. The atmosphere controls the evaporation of the solvent and the subsequent destabilization of the sols by solvent evaporation leading to a gelation process and the formation of a transparent film due to the small particle size in the sols (nm range) [55].

3.4. Physics and Chemistry of ZnO Derived from Sol-Gel Thin Film Technology

To capture the current ‘state of the art’ Zinc Oxide sol-gel methodology, an extensive review of publications [48-50] on this topic was undertaken. The reported studies were scrutinized for optimal processing conditions based on the criteria that the films formed were:

1. Free of visible physical defects such as cracks and pin holes.
2. Optical transmittance of 80% or more based on zinc oxide sol-gel literature reports [48-50] as benchmarks for transparency given a film thickness in the range of 200 to 500 nm.

The following summarizes findings from these reports:

3.4.1 Precursors

Metal salts are generally used as precursors due to low cost, facility of use and commercial availability. The metal salts can be both inorganic and organic. Inorganic salts like nitrates are often used, as precursors for sol-gel ZnO based material, even though their main drawback is the inclusion or difficult of anionic species in the final product [56-57]. Using zinc acetate as a precursor, the acetate groups, as contaminants of the gel, decompose under annealing producing volatile by-products [57]. Bahnemann *et. al.* [58] synthesized transparent colloidal suspensions of zinc oxide in water, 2-propanol, acetonitrile, and using different zinc salts. They have reported that the anion, in zinc salt, is critical for the preparation of transparent and stable ZnO colloids.

3.4.2 Solvents

The solvent in the sol-gel method of ZnO film preparation must have a relatively high dielectric constant so that it can dissolve the inorganic salts [59-61]. Most alcohols are dipolar, amphiprotic solvents with a dielectric constant that depends on the chain length [62]. Alcohols with low carbon number, up to 4, are mostly used as solvents such as methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 2-propanol, 1-butanol and 2-methoxyethanol. Among all the monoalcohols, the most used are the ethanol and 2-propanol. Hosono *et. al.* [60], studied the chemical reactions of zinc acetate dihydrate to ZnO preparation using different types of solvents, i.e. methanol, ethanol, and 2-methoxyethanol. Zinc acetate dihydrate

(ZAD) was more soluble in methanol than in ethanol or 2- methoxyethanol according to dielectric constants of these alcohols. After refluxing, intermediate product $Zn_5(OH)_8(Ac)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ called layered hydroxide zinc acetate (LHZA) is formed. This complex (LHZA) was also observed by Meulenkamp [63] using ethanol as a solvent and by Fujihara *et. al.* [64] and Wang *et. al.* [65] using methanol. Finally these complexes undergo hydrolysis and inorganic polymerization leading to the formation of sols consisting of zinc oxide nanoparticles.

3.4.3 Additives

Additives are chemical species having at least one functional group. They act as basic or acid and/or chelating agent. Alkali metal hydroxides, carboxylic acids, alkanolamines, alkylamines, acetylacetone and polyalcohols are used for this purpose. They facilitate the zinc salt dissolution in alcoholic media. ZAD has a limited solubility in alcohols like ethanol and 2-propanol in the absence of other agents or heating. The agents, like (mono- to tri-) ethanolamines or lactic acid help in complete dissolution and formation of a stable sol [66]. Furthermore, the additives play the role of chelating and stabilizing ligands, which avoid the rapid precipitation of zinc hydroxide and allow stable dispersions to be formed. The amino groups and/or the hydroxyl groups of alkanolamines coordinate the metal atoms of alkoxides, thus improving the solubility and stability against hydrolysis of the alkoxides [67]. The addition of alkanolamine in zinc acetate provides a clear solution. MEA a bidentate ligand, coordinate with zinc atoms; one way by acting as a chelating ligand and the other way so as to bridge two zinc atoms [67]. Inorganic bases, lithium or sodium hydroxide is used to form stable dispersions of colloids.

MEA acts as a complexing agent, which retards the Zn^{2+} condensation; however, its presence also increases the pH, which promote the formation of ZnO. The acetate group plays a very relevant role, by complexing Zn^{2+} in competition with the MEA. The complex chemical relationships of the main species are indicated in figure 1.4. The three nucleophilic species (MEA, HO^- and CH_3COO^-) compete for the Zn^{2+} Lewis acid center: attack of an HO^- group leads to the formation of small zinc-oxo-acetate oligomers, which are expected to be formed in the initial stage, from gradual forced hydrolysis of Zn-MEA or Zn-OCOCH₃ soluble complexes during aging. The progressive condensation of the hydrolyzed moieties gives rise to colloids or precipitates. This gives rise to stable acetate-capped colloidal nanometric particles in dilute solutions.

Figure 3.3 Chemical equilibria taking place in the initial solutions followed by Hydrolysis and condensation on heating which results in Soluble or colloidal condensed moieties that can be deposited as film precursors; [68].

3.4.4 Mixing of Solution:

There was a wide range of mixing conditions used. Several studies simply reported to ‘stir until a clear, homogenous solution is formed’. The time used to mix the solution ranged from 30 minutes to 2 hours. The temperatures ranged from room temperature to 100°C. Of course, the temperature would depend on the solvent but there was no clear cut picture of how much time was needed to ensure the metal cross linking had been established or if any time was needed at all. Similarly, in some of the studies the solutions were given time

to ‘age’. It was not reported whether this had any benefit. Although the optimal mixing time was not clearly indicated, a mixing time of 2 hours at 50 to 80° C (depending on solvent boiling point) appeared to ensure good ‘sol’ microstructure development.

3.4.5 Growth mechanisms

Spanhel and Anderson [69] have reported that there are two possible ways of describing the growth of ZnO crystals; by Ostwald ripening and by aggregation. In this growth process, as soon as the smallest stable molecular clusters are formed, they rapidly combine to give the next most stable aggregate. The primary aggregates then further rapidly combine to give the next most stable secondary aggregate and so on. Meulenkamp [70] suggested that the particle growth in colloidal systems can take place in two ways. The first one corresponds to Ostwald ripening: large particles grow at the expense of smaller particles, which have a higher solubility according to the so-called Ostwald–Freundlich equation. The second way describes growth by the addition of reactive precursors available in solution to already existing particles. The rate of particle growth is governed by the concentration of precursors or dissolved species and their reactivity, which depends on the number of particle surface atoms, and the solution composition. Tokumoto et. al. [71] reported that the formation of ZnO colloidal particles in an alcoholic solvent consists of two stages. During the early stage of phase transformation, small oligomers are continuously formed. At advanced stages, the aggregation of the oligomers leads to crystalline wurtzite, the primary colloidal particles. The primary particles then aggregate and form the secondary colloidal particles. The growth of the colloidal particles is a stepped, discontinuous, process which indicates that the predominant mechanism of aggregation is heterogeneous coagulation. This mechanism of growth leads to a hierarchical structure.

3.4.6 Nucleation and growth

It has been reported by Spanhel [72] that at least four different “primary particles or clusters” serving as initiators of the znO colloid growth, from ZAD as precursor, could be identified. The nature of these primary particles or clusters depends strongly on the synthesis chosen viz. initial salt concentration, the temperature and time of the thermal treatment, the nature of alcohol solvent as well as the humidity, storage and analysis conditions. Among these primary particles, are $Zn_5(OH)_8(Ac)_2 \cdot H_2O$ and $Zn_4O(Ac)_6$. In other respects, Meulenkamp [70], prepared ZnO nanoparticles by addition of LiOH to an

ethanolic zinc acetate solution. He showed that control of the particle size was improved by the influence of temperature, water, and reaction products during the aging of ZnO sols. Water and acetate accelerates the particle growth. Hu *et. al.* [73] have synthesized ZnO nanoparticles by precipitation from zinc acetate in a series of nalkanols from ethanol to 1 hexanol as a function of temperature.

The kinetics of nucleation and growth are expected to be strongly dependent on the properties of the solvent. For the shorter chain length alcohols, ethanol and 1-propanol, nucleation and growth are retarded compared to longer chain length alcohols, from 1-butanol to 1-hexanol, where nucleation and growth are fast. The particles size increases with increasing temperature for all solvents and increases with alkanol chain length. In fact, during the growth of colloidal ZnO nanoparticles, the alcohols not only provide the medium for the reactions, but also act as ligands to help to control the morphology and particle size of ZnO.

3.4.7 Film formation

In sol-gel method, ZnO films are prepared by dip- or spin-coating of substrate from sols freshly prepared or aged at room temperature or around 60°C. The deposited ZnO films must be dried at a high enough temperature to remove solvent and other organic compounds but not so high that the film begins to degrade. The rate of drying is also important and dependent on the kinetics of the mass transfer of precursor materials out of the sol-gel as well as the formation of the optimal crystal structure. A drying rate that is too rapid might result in film defects and/or no film at all. A drying rate that is too slow might be unnecessarily costly. Zinc Oxide thin film drying processes were generally separated into two stages: an initial drying step and a final annealing step. Thin film formation steps with heat treatment is depicted in figure 3.4.

3.4.8 Initial Drying Step

This initial drying was generally used in procedures that required repeated application of the sol – procedures such as spin coating [77] and dip coating [28]. The ‘initial drying’ resulted in the removal of the solvent phase and some of the organics since the MEA and acetate groups decompose at 200-400°C. There were several studies that looked at the initial drying time. As can be seen, no conclusive evidence could be drawn from this as to the best drying temperature.

Figure 3.4. Thin Film Formation Steps under heat treatment.

3.4.9 Final Annealing Process:

Following the drying step, an annealing step was done at 400- 600°C to remove any residual organics as well as to dehydrate zinc hydroxide to form the final Zinc Oxide film. Based on these studies, the best results for film formation appear to be anywhere from 400°C to 600°C [15].

Referring from TG-DTA analysis of M. F. Hossain et al. [15], a small endothermic peak and two exothermic peaks at 66, 258, and 310°C respectively from DTA curve are attributed to the evaporation of water and ethanol, caused by crystal conversion of ZnO from amorphous to wurtzite phase.

Figure 3.5. TG-DTA curve for ZnO xerogel [15]

3.5. Conclusion

To summarize, the sol-gel fabrication approach is capable of making high quality zinc oxide thin films which are free of defects, have good crystal development with c-axis orientation and which are more than 80% transparent. As a precursor use of Zinc Acetate (usually the dihydrate form) is popular and effective as the metallic salt. An alkaline pH using Diethanolamine (DEA) in a 1:1 molar ratio with Zinc Acetate can be used where as solvent organic solutions like ethanol, methanol, iso-propanol, n-butanol can be employed.

CHAPTER - 4
EXPERIMENTAL
SECTION

4.1. Introduction

The optical and structural properties of sol-gel derived ZnO thin films depend critically on several parameters such as pre heating and annealing temperature, concentration of solution, presence of polyethylene glycol (PEG) content, film thickness and so on [15-16]. Among these factors film thickness is directly related to the resistivity, crystallites size and orientation of ZnO films [25]. It has been reported that film thickness of sol-gel derived ZnO film is greatly dependent on the withdrawing rate and for uniform thickness of the films withdrawing rate must be constant [26]. But in conventional sol-gel process [21-23] dipping and withdrawing process is done manually, hence maintaining constant and smooth dipping or withdrawing rate is quite difficult. As a result the interference fringes will not remain constant and films thickness will be non-uniform. But automatic sol-gel process can be employed to overcome the drawbacks associated with the conventional sol-gel technique. In this work, ZnO thin films were deposited on different lengths of glass substrate (2-7 cm) by using previously reported [28] automatic dipping and withdrawing system. Four sets of ZnO thin films were prepared varying several parameters such as solution concentration, films thickness, and PEG content. Zinc acetate di-hydrate was used as a precursor and diethanolamine was used as stabilizer. After annealing the as-deposited films at 500 °C for 2 h they characterized with optical properties using UV/Visible spectrometer at room temperature within the wavelength range of 300-900 nm. Also comparison was made between automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films.

4.2. Operating principle of automatic sol-gel system

Referring from [28], homemade automatic dipping and withdrawing system for deposition of thin films is shown in Fig. 4.1. The whole system is arranged on a wooden basement. The main parts of the system are motor, plastic ribbon, damper weight, clip, beaker base and a keyboard. The clip is attached to a plastic ribbon, one end of which is coiled on the motor shaft. A damper weight is attached with the ribbon in order to keep it straight and to eliminate the swing and vibration as the ribbon is too thin to have continuous swing in the natural wind and exposed to vibration while the motor rotates. There are six keys, corresponding to six different lengths (2cm, 3cm, 4cm, 5cm, 6cm and 7cm), and a power switch on the keyboard.

After preparing the precursor solution, it is kept on the beaker base and the substrate is hanged on the clip. The length of the ribbon from motor shaft is so adjusted that the lower part of the substrate just touches the precursor solution. This adjustment can also be done

Figure 4.1 Image of complete setup of automatic dipping and withdrawing system [28].

with the help of level adjusting screws that are attached to the bottom of the beaker base. Then the power switch is turned on and one of the six keys is pressed according to the required length of the substrate on which thin films have to be deposited. One point must be remembered here that the length of clean substrate must be greater than the required length of substrate covered with thin films. Pressing one of the six keys causes the motor to start rotation, at the same time the ribbon is uncoiled from the motor shaft and the substrate starts to dip into the precursor solution at a constant rate of 1cm/min. When the required length of substrate is fully immersed into the solution the motor stops rotation for 10 seconds. After that it again starts to rotate but in opposite direction so that ribbon is coiled on the motor shaft automatically, that causes the substrate to be withdrawn from the solution at the same rate of dipping (i.e. 1cm/min). When the substrate has been fully withdrawn from the solution it is then unclipped from substrate holder and is moved away for heat treatment.

4.3. Fabrication of ZnO thin films using so-gel process

4.3.1. Parameters variation

In this work, ZnO thin films were prepared by varying several parameters that are shown in the following Fig. 4.2.

Figure 4.2. All variations made in this work for preparing ZnO thin films.

- I. First set of samples were prepared by maintaining same films thickness (~500 nm) for various zinc acetate concentration of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 mol/L. It was reported by [26] that, ZnO films with 0.4 mol/L zinc acetate concentration show the deposition rate of 50 nm/coatings and deposition rate increases with the increase of zinc acetate concentrations. Referring from this reported data, the required number of layers/coatings needed to maintain ~500 nm thickness of ZnO films are listed in the following Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 No. of layers given to maintain ~500 nm thickness of ZnO films for various concentrations

Concentration (mol/L)	Thickness(nm)/Layer [15]	Given no. of Layers	Obtained thickness (nm)
0.4	50	10	500
0.6	75	7	525
0.8	90	6	540
1.0	95	5	475
1.2	100	5	500

- II. Second set of samples were prepared with equal number of coatings for various zinc acetate concentrations of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 mol/L.
- III. Third set of samples were prepared to investigate the effect of addition of Polyethylene Glycol (PEG) content in zinc acetate precursor solution. Various amounts of PEG (0.2g, 0.35g, 0.5g, 0.75g, and 1.0g) were added separately in zinc acetate solution of 1.0 mol/L where amount of solvent was 25 ml.
- IV. Fourth set of samples were prepared by varying thickness of ZnO films on same concentration of zinc acetate (1.0 and 1.2 mol/L). Thickness was varied by varying the number of coatings (2, 3, 4, and 5 layers).

4.3.2 Steps ZnO thin films fabrication

Deposition of ZnO thin films using sol-gel dip coating consists of four processes; substrate cleaning, precursor solution preparation, substrate dipping and withdrawing, and heat treatment. The whole process [28] is depicted in the following Fig. 4.3.

Figure 4.3 Sol-gel dip coating processes for ZnO thin films deposition.

4.3.2.1 Cleaning of Substrate

A variety of substrates including glass microslides, FTO (Fluorine Doped Tin Oxide) glass substrate, special ITO (Indium Doped Tin Oxide) substrate, quartz, sapphire, and silicon can be used to deposit ZnO thin films. Substrates such as sapphire that have a somewhat better crystal match to Zinc Oxide Wurtzite tended to show better film crystal orientation. Similarly, putting a seed layer on the substrate would result in better crystal orientation [74]. However, given thick enough films and/or the right thermal treatment, all substrates had the potential to yield acceptable crystal orientation and optical transmittance.

In this work, glass microslides of 7 cm length were used for ZnO thin films and shown in the following Fig. 4.4.

Figure 4.4. Glass microslides for thin films deposition

Before depositing ZnO thin films, the glass substrate must be cleaned properly so that no dust particles remain on the substrate. If there are dust particles on some portion of the substrate, then no thin film will be grown on that portion. In order to clean substrates an ultrasonic cleaner was employed in this work.

An ultrasonic cleaner is a cleaning device that uses ultrasound (usually from 20–400 kHz) and an appropriate cleaning solvent (sometimes ordinary tap water) to clean delicate items. Cleaning normally lasts between three to several minutes. Ultrasonic cleaning uses high frequency sound waves to agitate in a liquid. Cavitation bubbles induced by the agitation act on contaminants adhering to substrates like metals, plastics, glass, rubber, and ceramics. This action also penetrates blind holes, cracks, and recesses. The intention is to thoroughly remove all traces of contamination tightly adhering or embedded onto solid surfaces. Objects must not be allowed to rest on the bottom of the device during the cleaning process, because that will prevent cavitations from taking place on the part of the object not in contact with water. The ultrasonic cleaner employed in this work is shown in the following Fig. 4.5.

Figure 4.5. Electronic Ultrasonic cleaner used for cleaning substrate

The cleaning procedures employed in the present work is given below:

1. Choosing the appropriate length of substrate.
2. Keeping the substrate in a culture dish with Ethanol (C_2H_5OH) such that substrates are fully immersed.
3. Keeping the dish on Ultrasonic cleaner base and cleaner must be filled with distilled water but level of water to be less than dish height.
4. Turning the Ultrasonic cleaner on and setting the cleaning time (Say 5 min or 10 min)
5. Drying the substrate with air compressor to remove ethanol.
6. Drying the substrate on the sun-light for a while.
7. Repeating the steps 2 to 5 keeping the substrate in dish with distilled water.

4.3.2.2 Preparation of precursor solution

I. Chemical reagents

ZnO precursor solution was prepared using absolute ethanol ($M = 46.07$, CH_3CH_2OH , EtOH) as solvent, zinc acetate di-hydrate ($M = 219.50$, $Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, ZAD) as precursor, diethanolamine ($M = 105.14$, $[CH_2(OH)CH_2]_2.NH$, DEA) as chelating agent and de-ionized water. In addition, for preparing fourth set of ZnO films Polyethylene glycol ($M = \text{variable}$, $C_2nH_4n+2O_{n+1}$, PEG) was used [25]. The amount of chemical reagents used for preparing different sets of ZnO films is listed in the Table 4.2. The molar ratio of DEA/ZAD used in this work was 1:1 and the molar ratio of de-ionized water/ZAD was of 2:1.

Table 4.2. Amounts of chemical reagents used in this work for different molar concentrations

Sets of ZnO films	EtOH (ml)	Concentration (mol/L)	ZAD (gm)	DEA(ml)	H ₂ O(ml)	PEG(gm)
First, Second and Fourth	100	0.4	8.78	3.86	1.44	-
		0.6	13.17	5.79	2.16	-
		0.8	17.56	7.72	2.88	-
		1.0	21.95	9.65	3.6	-
		1.2	26.34	11.58	4.32	-
	50	0.4	4.39	1.93	0.72	-
		0.6	6.59	2.89	1.08	-
		0.8	8.78	3.85	1.44	-
		1.0	10.98	4.82	1.8	-
		1.2	13.17	5.79	2.16	-
	20	0.4	1.76	0.77	0.29	-
		0.6	2.63	1.16	0.43	-
		0.8	3.51	1.54	0.58	-
		1.0	4.39	1.93	0.72	-
		1.2	5.27	2.32	0.86	-
Third	25	1.0	5.49	2.41	0.90	0.20
		1.0	5.49	2.41	0.90	0.35
		1.0	5.49	2.41	0.90	0.50
		1.0	5.49	2.41	0.90	0.75
		1.0	5.49	2.41	0.90	1.0

II. Precursor solution preparation procedures

In this work, ZnO films were deposited for various zinc acetate concentration with different amount of solvent which is listed in Table 4.2. ZnO precursor solution was prepared in the following way as shown in Flowchart 4.1. At first, specific amount of zinc acetate was dissolved into specific amount of absolute ethanol to yield specific concentrated solution and then was magnetically stirred for 20 min. The magnetic stirrer employed in this work is shown in Fig. 4.6. A milky solution, as shown in Fig. 4.7(a), was obtained where a specific amount of DEA with a molar ratio of DEA/ZAD as 1:1 and with a molar ratio of de-ionized water/ZAD as 2:1 specific amount de-ionized water was added into the emulsion. The solution was again stirred and a clear solution was obtained, as shown in 4.7(b) after about 15 min. Meanwhile, a homogeneous mixer of absolute ethanol and de-ionized water was prepared with a volumetric ratio of 8:2. Finally, the precursor solution was hydrolyzed with drop by drop addition of prepared mixer of ethanol and de-ionized water keeping the solution under continuous stirring. After about 2 hrs when the clear solution just turned into little

Flowchart 4.1. Preparation procedures of precursor solution (a) for first, second, and fourth sets of ZnO films, and (b) for third set of ZnO films.

whitish in color then hydrolyzing was stopped and the solution, as shown in Fig 4.7(c), and the solution was ready for deposition of ZnO thin films. The above procedures were wholly followed for preparing first, second, and fourth sets of ZnO films as shown in Flowchart 4.1(a).

But while preparing the third set of ZnO films, hydrolysis was not done but specific amounts of PEG was added into the solution of 1.0 mol/L using 25ml solvent. After addition of PEG the solution was stirred for at least 2 hrs for thoroughly mixing of PEG into the solution.

Figure 4.6. Magnetic stirrer used for stirring solution

Figure 4.7 Precursor solution after (a) mixing ZAD and EtOH, (b) after mixing DEA and H₂O, and (c) after hydrolyzing.

4.3.2.3 Substrate dipping and withdrawing

In this work, substrate dipping and withdrawing was done by automatic sol-gel system reported by [27] and described in art 4.2. Different lengths of substrates ranging from 2 cm to 7 cm were used for deposition of ZnO thin films. The whole dipping and withdrawing procedures have been discussed earlier. It is to be mentioned that the dipping and withdrawing rate was 1 cm/min while the interval between consequent dipping and withdrawing was 10s.

4.3.2.4 Heat treatment

After completing one dipping and withdrawing iteration the coated films were dried at room temperature for 24 h and then heated at 300⁰C in air for 1 h to decompose the precursor film to ZnO. After that another deposition cycle was carried out. After completing the required deposition cycles, the films were annealed at 500⁰C at a heating rate of 10⁰C/min and left at 500⁰C for 2 h.

4.4. Characterization of prepared ZnO films by UV Visible property

The optical behaviors of a semiconductor are investigated in terms of the three phenomena namely transmittance, reflectance and absorbance. Therefore, it is necessary to study the ultraviolet (UV), visible and infrared (IR) characteristics of the material [25]. The optical behavior of a material is generally utilized to determine its optical constants, n and k_0 . The absorption of radiation by any medium occurs through the excitation of electrons and photons and the photon-electron interactions. Then intensity of radiation is generally

attenuated in an exponential form of the type $\exp(-\alpha t)$ [28], where α is the absorption coefficient and related to the imaginary part of k_o of the refractive index by

$$\alpha = \frac{4\pi k_o}{\lambda} \quad (4.1)$$

The absorption coefficient of thin film can be measured by passing monochromatic light through the film under study and measuring the incident and transmitted beam intensity by a photosensitive detector. When a ray of monochromatic light incident perpendicularly to a flat section of the film, a portion of the incident light will be reflected and the remainder part will be transmitted into the film. The transmitted light can be absorbed by the film material.

In the fundamental absorption region the transmission T is given by [12]

$$T = A \exp\left(\frac{-4\pi k_o t}{\lambda}\right) \quad (4.2)$$

Where, k_o is the extinction coefficient. From the equation (3.10), t is the film thickness and λ is the wavelength of incident light. If $k_o \ll n$ then the principle variation of T occurs in the exponential term and the pre-exponential term A which accounts for reflecting effect is close to unity. Therefore,

$$T = \exp(-\alpha t) \quad (4.3)$$

Then from equation (3.11), we can write for the absorption coefficient,

$$\text{Absorption coefficient, } \alpha = 2.303 \log\left(\frac{T}{100}\right) \quad (4.4)$$

Hence, knowing the value of transmittance T the value of absorption coefficient α can be determined.

$$\text{Again, from the equation of photo energy, } E = h\nu = \frac{hc}{\lambda} = \frac{1240}{\lambda} \text{ (ev)} \quad (4.5)$$

Therefore, from the equation (3.13), the value of wavelength λ the value of band gap can be determined.

In this work, Optical spectra was measured in wavelength ranges $300 < \lambda < 900$ nm using a Halo SB-10 UV-visible spectrophotometer, as shown in Fig 4.8(a), for all the prepared ZnO films. Before placing a ZnO films in the slot of spectrometer base was corrected using a reference glass substrate. Optical transmittance of the films for normal incidence was obtained. Obtained transmittance (%T) values were plotted against wavelength to find the transmission spectra.

Using Beer–Lambert equation (Equation 4.1) optical absorption was found for each wavelength from corresponding transmittance (%T) data.

$$\text{Absorption} = 2\text{-Log(Transmittance)} \quad (4.6)$$

The direct and indirect allowed optical transitions between valance and conduction bands can be evaluated by fitting a straight line in strong absorption spectral region using the Tauc relationship as shown in Fig 4.8(b). According to Tauc law dependence of absorption co-efficient (α) on photon energy ($h\nu$) can be given by [75]

$$(\alpha h\nu) = A(h\nu - E_g)^r \quad (4.7)$$

Where α is the absorption co-efficient, A is the edge width parameter, and $h\nu$ is the photon energy, and r is a constant, for direct allowed transition r equals $\frac{1}{2}$ and for indirect allowed transition equals 2.

Figure 4.8 Characterization of optical properties (a) UV/Visible Spectrometer, and (b) example of Tauc plot for band gap calculation.

CHAPTER - 5
RESULTS AND
DISCUSSION

5.1. Introduction

This chapter deals with the experimental results of the prepared ZnO thin films. The chapter begins with the images of different lengths of substrates covered by ZnO thin films that have been deposited by automatic sol-gel process. All the prepared films have been characterized by optical properties with UV/Visible spectrometer in the wavelength range of 300-900 nm. Comparison between conventional sol-gel derived and automatic sol-gel ZnO films have been figured out. The transmittance of all the automatic sol-gel derived ZnO films has been found to be above 90% in the visible range. The direct and indirect allowed band gap has also been found with satisfactory value.

5.2. Deposited ZnO films with length controlled automatic sol-gel process

Figure 5.1 shows the images of ZnO films covered with different length of substrate prepared by length controlled automatic sol-gel process. It can be easily figured out that the automatic sol-gel system is successful in depositing ZnO thin films on the required length of substrate without any hazards. This is a key advantage of the automatic sol-gel system. It is also clearly shown that the surface of prepared films has been grown uniformly. All the films are visually transparent and the transparency is approximately above 80%. The measured optical properties also agree with visual transparency that has been discussed later.

Figure 5.1. Images of ZnO thin films covered with different length of substrate prepared by length controlled automatic sol-gel process, (a) 2 cm, (b) 3 cm, (c) 4 cm, (d) 6 cm, and (e) 7 cm.

Figure 5.2. Images of ZnO thin films (a) automatic and (b) conventional sol-gel derived.

Figure 5.3. Transmittance spectra of automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO thin films.

5.3. Comparison between automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films

5.3.1. For Zinc acetate concentration of 1.0 mol/L

Figure 5.3 shows the images of ZnO thin films prepared by both automatic and conventional sol-gel method. It can be clearly understood that automatic sol-gel derived ZnO films are visually more transparent than conventional derived ZnO films. Figure 5.4 shows the optical transmittance spectra of the prepared films. Both the films have a very sharp cut-off at around 380 nm wavelength and reaches to peak at around 400 nm. The films are highly transparent in the visible range and have low transmittance at the UV region. It is to be noted that the average transparency of automatic sol-gel derived ZnO films (90%) is higher than the conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films (85%) in the visible range. Figure 5.4 shows the absorption spectra of the prepared films where it is found that both the films have high and low absorption in the UV and visible range respectively. Conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films comparatively have more absorption in the visible range.

Figure 5.4. Optical absorbance spectra of automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films

Figure 5.5. Plot of $(\alpha hv)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ of ZnO thin films for (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

Fig. 5.5(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ of prepared both types of ZnO films. The optical band gap for direct allowed transition of the films have been determined from the extrapolation of the linear portion of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ at $\alpha=0$. Direct transition band gap is found to be of 3.20eV for both automatic sol-gel derived and conventionally prepared ZnO films. Fig. 5.5(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha hv)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ of both types of prepared ZnO films and band gap for indirect allowed transition has been determined by extrapolating the straight line portion of the spectrum at $\alpha=0$. The indirect allowed band gap of both types of prepared ZnO thin films has been found to be of 3.01eV. It is to be noted that the direct allowed band gap and as well as indirect allowed band gap of the ZnO films remained unaffected whether it has been made form automatic or conventional process.

Figure 5.6. Optical properties with PEG for automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO films showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance.

5.3.2. For PEG in 1.0 mol/L Zinc acetate solution

Figure 5.6 shows transmittance and absorbance spectra of ZnO thin films with PEG for automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO thin films. There have been found a sharp ultraviolet cut off in the region 375-380 nm wavelength of all the films. The band edge shifted towards larger wavelength with the inclusion of PEG for both sets of films. ZnO films derived from automatic sol-gel system shows better optical performance.

Figure 5.7. Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for automatic and conventional sol-gel derived ZnO thin films with 1.0 g PEG showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

Fig. 5.7(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ of prepared both types of ZnO films. The optical band gap for direct allowed transition of the films have been determined from the extrapolation of the linear portion of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ at $\alpha=0$. Direct transition band gap is found to be of 3.15eV for both automatic sol-gel derived and conventionally prepared ZnO films. Fig. 5.5(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ of both types of prepared ZnO films and band gap for indirect allowed transition has been determined by extrapolating the straight line portion of the spectrum at $\alpha=0$. The indirect allowed band gap ZnO thin films prepared from automatic sol-gel method has been found to be of 2.95eV which decreases to 2.85eV when it has been prepared conventionally.

5.4. Effect of Zinc acetate concentrations at same films thickness

Figure 5.8 shows the optical transmittance spectra of ZnO film of same thickness (~500nm) for various zinc acetate concentrations. All the films have a very sharp cut-off around 380 nm wavelength and reaches to peak at around 400 nm. The films are highly transparent in the visible range (average transparency >85%) and have low transmittance at the UV region. There was found a red shift in the band edge with the increase of molar concentrations. This implies the decrease in band gap.

Figure 5.8. Transmittance spectra for ZnO films of same thickness for various zinc acetate concentrations.

Figure 5.9. Optical absorbance spectra of ZnO films of same thickness for various zinc acetate concentrations.

The optical absorbance ZnO films of same thickness for various zinc acetate concentrations are shown in Figure 5.9. It is clearly shown that all of the films have high absorbance in the UV region and low absorbance in the visible range.

Fig. 5.10(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films of same thickness. Direct transition band gap is found to decrease from 3.21 eV to 3.18 eV with the increase of Zinc acetate concentration.. Fig. 5.10(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films of same thickness The indirect allowed band gap has also been found to decrease from 3.05 eV to 2.95 eV with the increase of concentrations.

Figure 5.10. Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films of same thickness showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

Figure 5.11. Optical properties of ZnO films with same number of coatings for various zinc acetate concentrations showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance.

5.5. Effect of various zinc acetate concentrations at same number of coatings

Figure 5.11 shows transmittance and absorbance spectra of ZnO films with same number of coatings for various zinc acetate concentrations. There have been found a sharp ultraviolet cut off in the region 375-380 nm wavelength for all the films. The band edge shifted towards larger wavelength with the increase of zinc acetate concentrations. Average transparency of all the films in the visible range is above 90% and also have higher absorbance in the UV region.

Figure 5.10. Plot of $(\alpha hv)^n$ vs. hv for ZnO films of same no. of coatings in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

Fig. 5.11(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films of same no. of coatings. Direct transition band gap is found to decrease from 3.21 eV to 3.12eV with the increase of Zinc acetate concentration. Fig. 5.10(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films of same no. of coatings. The indirect allowed band gap has also been found to decrease from 3.05eV to 2.98 eV with the increase of concentrations.

5.6 Investigation of the effect of addition of PEG content in zinc acetate precursor solution

Figure 5.12 shows the transmittance and absorbance spectra of PEG contented ZnO thin films. 1.0g PEG contented ZnO films show better optical performance than decreased amount PEG contented ZnO films. The band edge shifted towards larger wavelength with the decreased amounts of PEG content.

Fig. 5.13(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various PEG content. Direct transition band gap is found to vary between 3.18 eV to 3.10eV. Fig. 5.10(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with PEG content. The indirect allowed band gap has also been found to increase from 2.81eV to 3.03 eV with the increase of PEG content.

Figure 5.12. Optical properties with various PEG contented ZnO films showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance.

Figure 5.13. Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various PEG content showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

5.7. Varying thickness of ZnO films on same zinc acetate concentration

5.7.1. 1.0 mo/L concentrated Zinc acetate solution

Figure 5.14 shows the transmittance and absorbance spectra of PEG contented ZnO with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L. The band edge shifted towards larger wavelength with the increase of coatings i.e. thickness.

Figure 5.14 Optical properties ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance.

Figure 5.15. Plot of $(\alpha hv)^n$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

Figure Fig. 5.15(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L. Direct transition band gap is found to decrease from 3.21 eV to 3.11eV with the increase of thickness. Fig. 5.15(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha hv)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.0mol/L. The indirect allowed band gap has also been found to decrease from 3.07eV to 2.95 eV with the increase of thickness.

5.7.2. 1.2 mo/L concentrated Zinc acetate solution

Figure 5.16 shows the transmittance and absorbance spectra of PEG contented ZnO with various coatings for concentration of 1.2mol/L. As like 1.0 mol/L concentrated films band edge here also shifted towards larger wavelength with the increase of coatings i.e. thickness.

Figure Fig. 5.17(a) shows the plot of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.2mol/L. Direct transition band gap is found to decrease from 3.21 eV to 3.11eV with the increase of thickness. Fig. 5.17(b) shows the plot of $(\alpha hv)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.2mol/L. The indirect allowed band gap has also been found to decrease from 3.07eV to 2.90 eV with the increase of thickness.

Figure 5.16. Optical properties ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.2 mol/L showing in (a) transmittance and (b) absorbance.

Figure 5.17. Plot of $(\alpha hv)^n$ vs. hv for ZnO films with various coatings for concentration of 1.2 mol/L showing in (a) direct allowed transition ($n=2$), and (b) indirect allowed transition ($n=1/2$).

5.8. Optimized parameters for automatic sol-gel method

The automatic sol-gel method has been optimized with respect to optical properties of ZnO films considering for application in solar cells that has been listed in table 5.1. For first set, i.e. same films thickness, ZnO films with 1.0mol/L has been found to show better optical performance with 85% transmittance and 3.18eV direct band gap. Again, for same number of coatings 1.0mol/L

sample shows optimized results. With 93% transparency 1.0g PEG contents show better results than other PEG contents. For fourth set, 1.0mol/L shows better optical performance.

Table 5.1. Optimized parameters for automatic sol-gel method

Parameters	ZnO sample	Transparency	Direct band gap	Indirect band gap
Same thickness	1.0 mol/L	85%	3.18eV	2.98eV
Same coating	1.0 mol/L	90%	3.14eV	3.00eV
PEG	1.0g	93%	3.10eV	3.03eV
Thickness variations	1.0mol/L	90%	3.14eV	3.04eV

CHAPTER - 6
DEVELOPMENT OF
DIGITAL
SOL-GEL SYSTEM

6.1. Introduction

To overcome the problems of conventional sol-gel method automatic sol-gel system has been introduced which has been shown in the earlier chapter. But there are some limitations of the existing automatic sol-gel system. So, in this work a digital sol-gel system has been developed by overcoming the limitations of previous system. In this chapter modeling and synthesis of digital sol-gel system has been described with necessary circuit diagram and figure. Also the operating principle of the digital system has been given.

6.2. Problems and proposed improvements of existing automatic sol-gel system.

The existing automatic sol-gel system has some major limitations. First of all, is that the substrate dipping and withdrawing is not completely free from vibration. The plastic ribbon that has been used to convert the circular motion of stepper motor into linear motion, for dipping and withdrawing purpose, is the main reason of vibration on the substrate. As a remedy of this problem rack and pinion has been employed in the present work to convert circular motion into linear motion. Fig. 6.1 shows the limitations of the existing sol-gel system and as well as corresponding steps that have been taken in this work to overcome.

Figure 6.1 Limitations and improvements on existing automatic sol-gel system

In the previous automatic system there were only six press switches that were correspond to only six distinct lengths of substrate. On the other hand, in the present work in order to give input a matrix keypad has been used and any length of substrate from 1 mm to 70 mm can be used for thin film deposition. A constant dipping and withdrawing rate of 1 cm/min was available from the previous automatic sol-gel system. On the contrary, the present work deals with making the automatic system with separate and variable dipping and withdrawing rate (1-90 mm/min). Moreover, in order to observe the different stages of dip coating process a display unit has been included with the automatic system that has made the system more users friendly.

6.3. Block diagram representation of digital sol-gel system

Fig.6.2 shows the basic block diagram representation of digital sol-gel system. The main parts of the digital sol-gel system are dc power supply unit, matrix keypad, display unit, motor driver, stepper motor, rack and pinion, substrate holder and a microcontroller unit which is the heart of the automatic arrangement. DC power supply unit rectifies 220V ac supply into 5V and 12V dc that are supplied to various components of the system. The stepper motor used in this work is of 2-phase 12V dc bipolar stepper motor with 7.5° step angle, i.e. in 48 steps it completes one revolution. As motor driver a 15 pin IC named L298N has been used. Rack and pinion has been employed to convert the circular motion of stepper motor into linear motion and substrate holder has been attached to the rack. All controlling operations were governed by a microcontroller unit (ATmega16L). As a input device a 4x4 matrix keypad and as a display unit a 20x2 LCD character display has been used.

Figure 6.2. block diagram representation of digital sol-gel system

After giving input value through matrix keypad microcontroller sends out control signal to the motor driver to drive the stepper motor. According to the control signal, the stepper motor starts rotation either in clockwise or anticlockwise direction. Since the motor shaft is mechanically attached to the pinion, so the rack moves upward and downward direction with clockwise and anticlockwise rotation of stepper motor respectively. As a result the substrate holder also can move upward and downward direction and the work of substrate dipping and withdrawing is accomplished.

Figure 6.3. Complete setup of digital sol-gel system

6.4. Complete setup of digital sol-gel system

Fig. 6.3 shows the homemade digital sol-gel system. The whole structure is made of using 3 mm plastic sheet. The main parts of the system are stepper motor, rack and pinion,

substrate holder, beaker base, matrix keypad and LCD display. The motor stands at 10 inches above the ground and is mounted on stand made form plastic sheet. A circular gear called ‘pinion’ is tightly attached to the motor shaft, while a linear gear called ‘rack’ is mechanically adjusted to the pinion through support and bushing. A close view of rack and pinion structure is shown in Fig. 6.4. Now when the motor rotates, rotational motion is applied to the pinion causes the rack to move thereby translating the rotational motion of the pinion into the linear motion of the rack. Hence with clockwise and anticlockwise rotation of motor, the rack moves in upward and downward direction.

Figure 6.4. Close view of rack and pinion showing in (a) front view and (b) side view

A substrate holder is attached to the lower portion of the rack through a screw. A close view of substrate holder with and without substrate is shown in Fig 6.5. Fig. 6.5(a) shows the front view of substrate holder without substrate and Fig. 6.5(b) shows the side view of substrate without substrate. Substrate holder consists of two bases, one substrate base and other screw base, and a holding screw. There is a spacing of 0.5 cm between two bases and both of the bases are made from plastic sheet. After placing a substrate in free space between two bases, holding screw is made to rotate in clockwise direction so that the

substrate is locked with substrate base through holding screw. Again rotation of holding screw in anticlockwise direction releases the substrate from base.

A beaker base is mechanically attached to the motor stand which can be moved in upward and downward direction along the surface of the stand. Hence it can be placed at any position above the ground as per requirement. Moreover, the beaker base is also made from plastic sheet.

There is an instrument box beside the motor stand inside which electronic equipments have been placed. The surface of the box is equipped with a LCD display unit, a matrix keypad and a power switch. For various operation of the digital sol-gel system input is given via keypad after giving electrical power and various information are displayed on the display unit.

Figure 6.5. Substrate holder without substrate showing in (a) front view, (b) side view and (c) showing substrate holder with substrate

6.5. Operating principle of digital sol-gel system

The operating principle of digital sol-gel system is shown in Fig. 6.6. At first prepared precursor solution is kept on the beaker base and a clean substrate is hung on the substrate holder. The motor shaft is adjusted in such a way that the rack is held in maximum upward position. After that the beaker base is adjusted so that the lower portion of the substrate just touches the upper surface of the precursor solution. It is to be noted that the length of the substrate must be 1.5 cm greater than the required length of substrate to be coated with thin films.

Figure 6.6. Operating principle of digital sol-gel system

After making the primary setup, power switch from the instrument box is turned on and a message “Welcome to Digital Sol-gel System” comes out on display. After 2 sec it is needed to input four distinct values for dip coating process. At first required length of substrate is given as a value of “L” that must be a numeric value ranging from 1 mm to 70 mm. Then dipping rate of substrate is given as a value of “D_r” ranging from 1 to 90mm/min. Third input value is the waiting time which is applicable after complete dipping of the substrate and is given as a value of “T”. The value of “T” must of three digits as like 005s, 010s, 120s, and so on. Finally as a value of “W_r” withdrawing rate is given, range of this is same as dipping rate. If any mistake occurs when giving any one of the four input values then it cannot be cleared instantly as there is no clear button in this system. It is needed to be continued to give input value and after giving the fourth input value cursor will again come back to first position. Then carefully input to be given from first. There must not to be made hurry while pressing two keys one after another. Because intentionally there have been made a delay of 0.4s between two keys pressing for programming purpose. There is no function of the keys named A, B, C and *.

After correctly giving all of the input values from keyboard it is needed to press “D” key to start dipping. Just after pressing “D” motor starts to rotate in anticlockwise direction to move the substrate in downward direction at a rate of “D_r” and a message “Dipping in Progress” will be shown on the display. After complete dipping of “L” length of the substrate motor stops for “T” sec and a message “Dipping completed----->Waiting----->” is displayed. After waiting “T” sec motor again starts rotation but now in clockwise direction so that the substrate is withdrawn from the solution at a rate of “W_r” and display will show the message “Withdrawing in Progress”. Finally after withdrawing “L” length of substrate motor stops permanently and alarm sound is heard along with message “Withdrawing completed”. Then from keyboard “#” button is needed to press to stop the alarm and to break the current operation.

After breaking the current operation, at first the power switch must be turned off for better lifetime of the electronic equipments. Then the substrate is removed from substrate holder for heat treatment. Again to coat another substrate with thin films new substrate to be hanged on the substrate holder and the whole process described above is to be repeated.

6.6. Internal circuitry arrangements of the digital system

Fig. 6.7 shows the complete circuit diagram of the digital sol-gel system. Since all the ICs and the stepper motor used in this work need dc power, hence a rectifier circuit is implemented as shown in Fig. 6.7(a). At first, the conventional 220V ac supply has been stepped down to 24V ac, using a stepped down transformer, which has been further rectified using a bridge rectifier. The output of the rectifier has been found to be of pulsating dc and hence has been filtered using 1000 μ F capacitor to get pure 24V dc. After

that, this dc voltage has been fed to LM7805 and LM7812 voltage regulators to have regulated 5V dc and 12V dc respectively. The voltage regulator has inherent advantages that dc output voltage remains unaffected with the change of load current. Microcontroller and LCD display requires 5V dc, while 12V dc has been supplied to stepper motor through motor driver.

Figure 6.7. Complete circuit diagram of digital system showing in (a) dc power supply unit, and (b) interconnection of microcontroller with stepper motor, keypad and LCD display.

Fig. 6.7(b) shows the electrical interconnection of microcontroller ATmega16L with stepper motor, through motor driver circuit, matrix keypad and LCD display. The software program for microcontroller has been written in C Language and then compiled to 'HEX-

file' using the WinAVR software. The compiled program has been burnt on ATmega16L chip using STK200 Programmer which is a parallel port/printer port burner. The simulation of the work has been carried out using Proteus simulator.

ATmega16L is a 40 pin DIP that has four 8-bit input/output ports named PortA, PortB, PortC and PortD. In this work, PortB have been used as input port connected through matrix keypad. While PortA and PortD has been used as output port connected through motor driver and LCD display respectively. A 4 MHz crystal oscillator has been connected between XALT1 and XALT2. +5V dc power supply has been given to VCC pin and GND pin has been solidly grounded. In order to understand the healthy condition of the microcontroller a LED has been connected to PC₀ through a 1K Ω resistor. Actually, microcontroller generates a 1 sec pulse at PC₀ hence the LED blinks at 1 sec interval. Finally, a buzzer has been connected to PC₁ through 680 Ω resistor that gives sound complete withdrawing of substrate.

In this work 4x4 matrix keypad has been interfaced with the microcontroller. Actually this type of matrix keypad is nothing but a combination of four rows and four columns and in between each overlapping row and column line there is a key as shown in fig. 6.8. Fig. 6.7(b) shows that Row1 to Row4 has been connected to PB₄ to PB₇, while Col1 to Col4 has been connected to PB₀ to PB₃ of microcontroller respectively.

LCD display used in this work is of 20x2 character type. Among eight data pins of LCD only D₀ to D₃ has been connected to the PD₄ to PD₇ of microcontroller respectively. Rs, Rw and E pins of LCD have been connected to PD₀ to PD₂ respectively. +5V dc power supply has been given to the LED+ through 330 Ω resistor and LED- has been solidly grounded along with V_{SS} and V_{EE}.

Figure 6.8. Architecture of matrix keypad

Motor driver L298N used in this work is a dual full-bridge driver in a 15-lead multiwatt package. It has four inputs and four corresponding output pins, *viz.* Out1 corresponds to In1. There are two enable pins, where ENA corresponds to In1 & In2 and ENB corresponds to In3 & In4. If an enable pin is high and one of two input pins is high then corresponding output pin get connected to supply voltage of stepper motor. According to Fig. 6.7(b) logic supply of +5V dc is connected to Vcc whereas supply voltage needed for stepper motor, i. e. 12V, is connected to V_S. SensA, SensB and GND is solidly grounded. Input pins In1 to In4 are directly connected to PA₃ to PA₀ of microcontroller respectively. Two enable pins are connected two +5V dc, hence when one of the input pins of L298N goes high then corresponding output pin goes high. The four output pins are connected to the four leads of the stepping motor as shown in the circuit diagram.

For a bipolar stepper motor there are two windings and a sequence of power is needed supply at each of the four terminals for rotation of the stepper motor. Hence clockwise or anticlockwise rotation and speed of rotation depends on the power given to the terminals of the stepper motor. Hence according to circuit diagram, PA₃ to PA₀ output pins of microcontroller can drive the stepper motor by proper sequence of power input to the motor.

In order to rotate the motor in clockwise and anticlockwise direction, the order in which the output pins of L298N are made to go to high state is shown in Fig 6.9. The eight diodes have been used to take care of inductive current generated when the respected windings remain turned off.

Figure 6.9. Pulse sequences of microcontroller to run the stepper motor

Fig. 6.10 and Fig. 6.11 show the electrical interconnections of equipments in project board and PCB board respectively. PCB board and the transformer are kept inside the instrument box while power switch, LCD display and matrix keypad are attached to the

upper surface of the box. The stepper motor is mounted on a stand beside the box and has been connected to the PCB board through wire.

Figure 6.10. Electrical connections of equipments in project board

Figure 6.11. Electrical connections of equipments in PCB board

CHAPTER - 7
CONCLUSION &
FUTURE WORK

7.1. Conclusion

The work reported in this thesis is mainly focused on firstly, to optimize the automatic sol-gel system and secondly, to develop a digital sol-gel system.

Starting with aim of the work, ZnO thin films were successfully prepared by automatic sol-gel dip coating technique. After annealing the as-deposited films at 500^{°C} for 2h, optical properties were measured and their performances over ZnO films prepared by conventional sol-gel process were investigated. The transmittance of the ZnO films (90%) obtained from automatic dip coater was well above than that of ZnO films (83%) prepared by conventional process. This indicates that smooth withdrawing rate has a great impact on the optical performance of ZnO films at it causes the interference fringes to remain constant and thus producing films with uniform thickness. But the direct band gap and as well as indirect band gap of the ZnO films remained unaffected whether it was made form automatic or conventional process. The automatic sol-gel system was finally optimized with respect to the optical properties of ZnO films considering for the application in solar cell by taking into account of different parameters variation.

While working with existing automatic sol-gel system there had been found some limitations of it. Hence an attempt was taken to develop a digital sol-gel system and the system was successfully fabricated. Modeling and synthesization of the digital sol-gel system has been clarified with necessary circuit diagram and figures. Hence both of the major two objectives of this thesis have been fulfilled successfully.

7.2. Future work

This thesis represents the detailed study about the fabrication of ZnO films with automatic sol-gel system for various applications like transparent conductive oxide, UV detector, optical window, DSSC solar cells, waste water purification, air purification etc. Again in order to overcome the limitations associated with automatic sol-gel system a digital sol-gel system has been fabricated. Future directions related to the work in this thesis are presented below:

1. Characterization of the prepared films with electrical properties
2. Characterization of the prepared films with structural properties (GIXRD, AFM, SEM)
3. Optimization of the digital sol-gel system with electrical, optical, structural and other properties of thin films.
4. To improve the digital system with necessary corrections like implementing a stepper motor of smaller step angle to have smaller linear displacement with one step.

References

- [1] Lu, G. Q. & Zhao, X. S. Nanoporous materials- an overview. *Series on Chemical Engineering* 4, 1-13 (2004).
- [2] Rao, C. N. R., Mueller, A. & Cheetham, A. K. Nanomaterials - An introduction. *Chemistry of Nanomaterials* 1, 1-11 (2004).
- [3] Kear, B. H. & Skandan, G. Overview: status and current developments in nanomaterials. *International Journal of Powder Metallurgy (Princeton, New Jersey)* 35, 35-37 (1999).
- [4] Tolles, W. M. & Rath, B. B. General overview on nanomaterials. *Nanomaterials: Synthesis, Properties and Applications*, 545-553 (1996).
- [5] Lin, Y.-W., Huang, M.-F. & Chang, H.-T. Nanomaterials and chip-based nanostructures for capillary electrophoretic separations of DNA. *Electrophoresis* **26**, 320-330 (2005).
- [6] Sing, K. S. W., Everett, D. H., Haul, R. A. W., Moscou, L., Pierotti, R. A., Rouquerol, J. & Siemieniewska, T. Reporting physisorption data for gas/solid systems with special reference to the determination of surface area and porosity (Recommendations 1984). *Pure and Applied Chemistry* **57**, 603-19 (1985).
- [7] Brinker, C. J., Wallace, S., Raman, N. K., Sehgal, R., Samuel, J. & Contakes, S. M. Sol-gel processing of amorphous nanoporous silicas: Thin films and bulk. *Access in Nanoporous Materials, [Proceedings of a Symposium on Access in Nanoporous Materials], East Lansing, Mich., June 7-9, 1995*, 123-139 (1995).
- [8] Dave, B. C., Dunn, B. & Zink, J. I. 21 pp (Dep. Materials, California Univ., Los Angeles, CA, USA., 1995).
- [9] Vossen, J.L. & Kern, W. Thin Film Processes II. Elsevier. 502 p. ISBN 978-0-12-728251-0.
- [10] Buschow, K.H.J., Cahn, R.W., Flemings, M.C., Ilschner, B., Kramer, E.J. & Mahajan, S. Encyclopedia of Materials - Science and Technology, Volumes 1-11. Elsevier. 3576 p. ISBN 978-0-08-043152-9.
- [11] Klein, L.C. 1988. Sol-Gel Technology for Thin Films, Fibers, Preforms, Electronics and Specialty Shapes. William Andrew Publishing/Noyes. 6p. ISBN 978-0-8155-1154-0.
- [12] S. A. Kamaruddin, K. Y. Chan, H. K. Yow, M. Z. Sahdan, H. Saim, D. Knipp, *Appl. Phys. A* 104, 263 (2011). doi10.1007/s00339-010-6121-2

- [13] S. S. Shariffudin, M. Salina, S. H. Herman, and M. Rusop, *Trans. on Electric. and Electro. Mater.* 13, 102 (2012). doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.4313/TEEM.2012.13.2.102
- [14] A. Janotti and C. G. V. d. Walle, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* 72, 126501 (2009). doi:10.1088/0034-4885/72/12/126501
- [15] M. F. Hossain, S. Biswas, M. Shahjahan, and T. Takahashi, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol.* 27, 1047 (2009). doi: 10.1116/1.3139887
- [16] M. F. Hossain, Z. H. Zhang and T. Takahashi, *Nano-Micro Lett.* 2, 53 (2010). doi: 10.5101/nml.v2i1.p53-55
- [17] M. F. Hossain, T. Takahashi, and S. Biswas, *Electro. Commu.* 11, 1756 (2009). doi:10.1016/j.elecom.2009.07.011
- [18] A. Ohtomo, M. Kawasaki, T. Koida, K. Masubuchi, H. Koinuma, Y. Sakurai, Y. Yoshida, T. Yasuda, and Y. Se-gawa, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 72, 2466 (1998). doi:10.1063/1.121384
- [19] J. H. Lee and B. O. Park, *Thin Solid Films* 426, 94 (2003). doi:10.1016/S0040-6090(03)00014-2
- [20] C. Lennon, R. Kodama, Y. Chang, S. Sivanathan, M. Deshpande, *J. Electro. Mater.* 37, 1324 (2008). doi:10.1007/s11664-008-0436-1
- [21] L. Znaidi, G.J.A.A. Soler Illia, S. Benyahia, C. Sanchez, A.V. Kanaev, *Thin Solid Films* 428, 257 (2003). DOI:10.1016/S0040-6090(02)01219-1
- [22] M. Ohyama, H. Kozuka and T. Yoko, *Thin Solid Films* 306, 78 (1997). doi:10.1016/S0040-6090(97)00231-9
- [23] M. Caglar, S. Ilican and Y. Caglar, *Thin Solid Films* 517, 5023(2009). doi:10.1016/j.tsf.2009.03.037
- [24] Z. Liu, Z. Jin, W. Li, J. Qiu, *Mater. Lett.* 59, 3620 (2005). doi:10.1016/j.matlet.2005.06.064
- [25] S. Paul, and M. F. Hossain, "Investigation of Optical Properties of ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Sol-gel Method", 2013 *International Conference on Mechanical, Industrial and Materials Engineering (ICMIME)*, vol. 1, pp. 748-753, Nov. 2013, RUET, Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
- [26] S. Paul, M. F. Hossain, M. H. Islam, M. F. Ali and U. Shaha, "Synthesization of ZnO thin films by length controlled automatic sol-gel process," 2013 *International Conference on Informatics, Electronics and Vision (ICIEV)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2013, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICIEV.2013.6572666.

- [27] Md. Feroz Ali, Utpal Saha, "Design a low cost and automatic dipping and withdrawing system for the deposition of thin films", *B.Sc. Dissertation*, EEE, RUET, 2012.
- [28] S. Paul, M. F. Hossain, M. H. Islam, M. A. Raihan and S. Chakladar, "Optical properties of ZnO thin films prepared by automatic sol-gel method," 2013 International Conference on Electrical Information and Communication Technology (EICT), Khulna, Bangladesh, 2014, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/EICT.2014.6777906.
- [29] G. John, G. Mary, Richard Feynman: A Life in Science. Dutton. 1997 p. 170. ISBN 0452276314.
- [30] Eric, Drexler "The promise that launched the field of nanotechnology". *Metamodern: The Trajectory of Technology*. Retrieved 13 May 2011.
- [31] Toumey, Chris (2008. *Techné* 13 (3): 133–168.
- [32] Takuya Tsuzuki, "Commercial scale production of inorganic nanoparticles", *Int. J. Nanotech.* 6 (2009) 567.
- [33] Huang, Y.-X.; Liu, X.-W.; Sun, X.-F.; Sheng, G.-P.; Zhang, Y.-Y.; Yan, G.-M.; Wang, S.-G.; Xu, A.-W.; Yu, H.-Q. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 2011, 36, 2773–2776
- [34] Wang, Y.; Yao, J.; Li, H.; Su, D.; Antonietti, M. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2011, 133, 2362–2365.
- [35] <https://depts.washington.edu/spirolab/researchpro.html>. Accessed January 07, 2014
- [36] Hillie, Thembela; Hlophe, Mbhuti (2007). *Nature Nanotechnology* 2 (11): 663–664. doi:10.1038/nnano.2007.350. PMID 18654395.
- [37] B.O' Regan and M. Grätzel, *Nature* 353 (1991) 737.
- [38] M.A. Green, K. Emery, K. Bücher, D.L. King and S.Igari, *Prog. Photovoltaics: Res. Appl.* 6 (1998) 35-42
- [39] Carrara, S., Cavallini, A., De Micheli, G., "*Multi-panel Drugs Detection in Human Serum for Personalized Therapy*", *Biosensors*, vol. 28, May 26, 2010.
- [40] Peter M. Martin, "Handbook on deposition technologies for films and coatings", 2005, ISBN–13: 978-0-8155-2031-3
- [41] Kappertz, O. et al. 'Reactive sputter deposition of zinc oxide: Employing resputtering effects to tailor film properties'. *Thin Solid Films*. 2005.
- [42] Heo, Y. W. et al. 'Origin of green luminescence in ZnO thin film grown by molecularbeam epitaxy'. *Journal of Applied Pyhsics*. 2005.
- [43] Martins, R et al. 'Zinc Oxide as an ozone sensor'. *American Institute of Physics*. 2004.

- [44] Villanueva, Yolanda et al. 'Pulsed laser deposition of zinc oxide'. *Thin Solid Films*. 2006.
- [45] Mosbah, A. et al. 'Comparison of the structural and optical properties of zinc oxide thin films deposited by d.c. and r.f. sputtering and spray pyrolysis'. *Surface Coatings & Technology*. 2005.
- [46] Green Econometrics. 'Understanding the Cost of Solar Energy' 05/04/09. http://greenecon.net/understanding-the-cost-of-solar-energy/energy_economics.html.
- [47] Krunks, Malle, Mellikov, Enn. 'Zinc oxide thin films by the spray pyrolysis method'. *Thin Solid Films*. 1995.
- [48] O'Brien, Shane, Koh, L.H.K, Crean, Gabriel M., ZnO thin films prepared by a single step sol-gel process, *Thin Solid Films*, 516, 2008.
- [49] Srinivasan, G., Kumar, J., 'Optical and structural characterization of Zinc Oxide thin films prepared by sol-gel process' *Crystal Research Technology*, 41, No. 9, 893 (2006).
- [50] Hongxia Li, Jiyan Wang, Hong Liu, Huaijin Zhang, Xia Li, 'Zinc Oxide films prepared by sol-gel method', *Journal of Crystal Growth* 275 (2005) e943-e946.
- [51] Lamia Znaidi, *Mater. Sci. Engg. B.*, 174 (2010) 18.
- [52] (a) J. Livage, D. Ganguli, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* , 68 (2001) 365.
- [53] Mehrotra, R.C., Singh, A.: Recent trends in metal alkoxide chemistry. *Prog. Inorg. Chem.* **46**, 239–454 (1997)
- [54] C. J. Brinker , G. C. Frye, A. J. Hurd And C. S. Ashley, "Fundamentals of sol-gel dip coating," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 201, pp. 97-108, 1991.
- [55] C. Jeffrey Brinker And Alan J. Hurd, "Fundamentals of sol-gel dipcoating," *J.Phys. III France*, vol. 4, pp. 1231-1242, July 1994.
- [56] Inoue, M., Kominami, H., Inui, T.: Novel synthetic method for the catalytic use of thermally stable zirconia: Thermal decomposition of zirconium alkoxides in organic media. *Appl. Catal.*, A **97**, L25–L30 (1993)
- [57] Inoue, M., Kominami, H., Otsu, H., Inui, T.: Synthesis of microcrystalline titania in organic media. *Nippon Kagaku Kaishi* pp. 1364–1366 (1991)
- [58] Ivanda, M., Music, S., Popovic, S., Gotic, M.: XRD, Raman and FT-IR spectroscopic observations of nanosized TiO₂ synthesized by the sol-gel method based on an esterification reaction. *J. Mol. Struct.* **481**, 645–649 (1999).
- [59] M.Z.-C. Hu, E.A. Payzant, C.H. Byers, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 222 (2000) 20.
- [60] E. Hosono, S. Fujihara, T. Kimura, H. Imai, *J. Sol–Gel Sci. Technol.*, 29 (2004) 71.

- [61] D. Sun, M. Wong, L. Sun, Y. Li, N. Miyatake, H.J. Sue, *J. Sol–Gel Sci. Technol.*,43, (2007) 237.
- [62] Z. Hu, G. Oskam, P.C. Searson, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*,263 (2003) 454.
- [63] E.A. Meulenkaamp, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 102 (1998) 5566.
- [64] S. Fujihara, E. Hosono, T. Kimura, *J. Sol–Gel Sci. Technol.*, 31 (2004) 165.
- [65] H. Wang, C. Xie, D. Zeng, *J. Cryst. Growth*, 277 (2005) 372.
- [66] S. Chakrabarti, D. Ganguli, S. Chaudhuri, *Mater. Lett.* 58 (2004) 3952.
- [67] M. Ohyama, H. Kozuka, T. Yoko, S. Sakka, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 104 (1996) 296.
- [68] L. Znaidi, G.J.A.A. Soler Illia, S. Benyahia, C. Sanchez, A.V. Kanaev, *Thin Solid Films* 428 (2003) 257.
- [69] L. Spanhel, M.A. Anderson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 113 (1991) 2826.
- [70] E.A. Meulenkaamp, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 102 (1998) 5566.
- [71] M.S. Tokumoto, S.H. Pulcinelli, C.V. Santilli, A.F. Craievich, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 247 (1999) 176.
- [72] L. Spanhel, *J. Sol–Gel Sci. Technol.* 39 (2006) 7.
- [73] Z. Hu, G. Oskam, P.C. Searson, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 263 (2003) 454.
- [74] Zhang, Canyon. High-quality oriented ZnO films grown by sol-gel process assisted with ZnO seed layer?. *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*. 2010.
- [75] N. Shakti, P. S. Gupta, “Structural and optical properties of sol-gel prepared ZnO thin film”, *Applied Physics Research*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 19-28, 2010.
- [76] M. H. Islam, M. F. Hossain, S. Paul, M. Fardousi, “Implimentation of Computer-controlled Electrodeposition methodology for Depositing Metal Oxide Thin Films”, 2013 International Conference on Mechanical, Industrial and Materials Engineering (ICMIME), vol. 1, pp. 740-747, Nov. 2013, RUET, Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
- [77] M. F. Hossain, S. Paul, M. A. Raihan and M. A. Goffar Khan, "Fabrication of digitalized spin coater for deposition of thin films," 2014 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Information & Communication Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2014, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICEEICT.2014.6919158.

Appendix

List of publications

Published papers

1. **S. Paul**, D. M. F. Hossain, M. H. Islam, M. F. Ali, and U. Shaha, “Synthesization of ZnO thin films by length controlled automatic sol-gel process “, *Int. Conf. Inf. Electro. Vission*, 1, 85 (2013). [doi:10.1109/ICIEV.2013.6572666](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEV.2013.6572666)
2. **S. Paul**, and M. F.Hossain , “Investigation of Optical Properties of ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Sol-gel Method”, *ICMIME*, pp.748-753, 2013.
3. M.F. Hossain, **S. Paul**, M. T. Islam , M. Sarkar, “Hybrid Power System for Rural Areas of Bangladesh”, *ICECTE*, pp. 386-389, 2012
4. M. H. Islam, M. F. Hossain, **S Paul**, M. Fardousi , “Implimentation of Computer-controlled Electrodeposition methodology for Depositing Metal Oxide Thin Films”, *ICMIME*, pp. 740-747, 2013

Accepted paper:

1. **S. paul**, M. F. Hossain, M. Islam, M. A.Raihan, S. Chakladar, “Optical Properties of ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Automatic Sol-gel Method”, *EICT*, 2013.